

**BERGISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WUPPERTAL**

Faculty of Electrical Engineering,
Information Technology and Media Technology

Chair of Automation Engineering / Computer Science

Master Thesis

**LMI-Based Control of a Nonlinear Overhead Crane Model Using
Local Model Networks**

Yilmaz Ener
1164993

M.Sc. Electrical Engineering

Wuppertal, 29 September 2022

Supervisor	Dr.-Ing. Robert Dehnert	First Examiner	Prof. Dr.-Ing. B. Tibken
		Second Examiner	Prof. Dr.-Ing. S. Butzmann

Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that I have written this thesis independently, have not used any sources or aids other than those indicated, and have marked all quotations as such.

Wuppertal, 29 September 2022

(Signature)

Consent for Publication

I agree that my thesis may be made available to scientifically interested persons or institutions. Correction or evaluation remarks in my work may not be cited.

Wuppertal, 29 September 2022

(Signature)

Kurzfassung

Am Lehrstuhl für Automatisierungs- und Regelungstechnik der Bergischen Universität Wuppertal wird an der Entwicklung von Steuerungen für Krananlagen geforscht. Hierfür wurde ein Labortest einer Ladebrücke zur Verfügung gestellt, die in Betrieb genommen wurde. Ziel ist hier die Erstellung eines mathematischen Modells mit dem Local Linear Neuro-Fuzzy-Verfahren. Brückenkrananlagen sind aufgrund ihres effizienten Transports in der Logistik weit verbreitet. Die Parameter des Kransystems können mit dem Transport variieren, daher sollte die Anti-Roll-Steuerung so ausgelegt sein, dass sie unempfindlich gegenüber Schwankungen der Systemparameter ist. Die Fokussierung auf das reine Entwurfsproblem des adaptiven Neuro-Fuzzy-Tracking-Controller-Modells erfordert keine Parameter aus dem Kransystem, zum Beispiel Traglastmasse, Kranseillänge oder Position und Geschwindigkeit. Das System wird als Black-Box-Modell konzipiert und benötigt daher nur gemessene Eingangsdaten und Ausgangsdaten. Die Lyapunov-Methode wird verwendet, um die Gewichtsaktualisierungsregel des Neuro-Fuzzy-Modells zu entwerfen, und die Robustheit des vorgeschlagenen Controllers wird durch die LMI-basierte Lyapunov-Stabilitätstheorie bewiesen.

Abstract

At the chair for automation and control technology at the Bergische University Wuppertal, research is being carried out into the development of controls for crane systems. For this purpose, a laboratory test of a loading bridge was made available, which has been put into operation. The aim here is to create a mathematical model with the Local Linear Neuro-Fuzzy method. Overhead crane systems are widely used in logistics due to their efficient transport. The parameters of the crane system can vary with transportation, so the anti-roll controller should be designed so that it is insensitive to fluctuations in system parameters. Focusing on the pure design problem of the adaptive neuro-fuzzy tracking controller model, does not required any parameter from crane system, for example caren mass, payload mass, crane cable length or postion and velocity. the system will be desinged as Black-Box model therefore required just mesuared inputs data and outputs data. The Lyapunov method is used to design the weight update rule of the neuro-fuzzy model, and the robustness of the proposed controller is proved by the LMI based Lyapunov stability theory.

Contents

List of Figures	VI
List of Tables	VIII
1 Introduction	1
2 Basics	3
2.1 System Description	3
2.1.1 Nonlinear State Space Representation	4
2.1.2 Linearization	4
2.2 System Identification	7
Black-Box, Gray-Box and White-Box Models	7
2.3 Local Model Networks	9
2.3.1 Mathematical Formulation of Local Model Networks	10
2.3.2 Local Linear Model Trees - LOLIMOT- Procedure of the LOLIMOT Algorithm	13 14
2.3.3 Determination of Dynamic Orders of the Model	15
2.3.4 Parameter Optimization	16
2.3.5 Structure Optimization	18
2.3.6 Local Approximation	20
2.3.7 Global Approximation	22
2.3.8 Normalized Mean Square Error	23
2.3.9 LOLIMOT Model Output Approximation	24
2.3.10 Local Model Networks for Identifying Nonlinear State Space Models	24
2.4 Standard Control Loop	27
2.5 Discretization	27
2.6 State Controller Using LMI	30
2.6.1 Linear Combination of System Matrices and Stability Analysis	30
2.6.2 State Observer Design Based on Linear Matrix Inequalities . .	31
2.6.3 State Controller Design Based on Linear Matrix Inequalities .	33
A Parameter-Independent Lyapunov Function Approach for Control Design	34
2.6.4 Calculation of Control Performance for LMI-Based State Con- troller	35
3 Basics of the Loading Bridge	36
3.1 Mathematical Model of the System	38
3.2 Lagrange Equations for Dynamic Systems	39

3.3	Equation of Motion of the System	41
3.3.1	State Space Representation of the Nonlinear Model	41
3.3.2	Quasi-Linearization of the Nonlinear System	44
3.3.3	Linearized Model	47
3.3.4	Luenberger Observer and State Controller	51
4	Model Building	55
4.1	Tasks in Model Building	55
4.1.1	Model Inputs of the Black-Box Model	55
4.1.2	Excitation Signals of the LOLIMOT Model	56
4.1.3	Choice of Model Architecture	58
4.1.4	Dynamic Orders of the LOLIMOT Model	59
4.1.5	Model Structure and Complexity	59
4.1.6	Optimization of Model Parameters	60
4.1.7	Model Validation	60
	Model Results of RMSE and Quality Measures	62
4.2	State Space Representation of the Best Local Model Network	65
4.3	Linear Combination of the Local Models	69
5	Design of Observer-Based State Control	71
5.1	LMI-based Observer using LOLIMOTSS	71
5.2	LMI-based State Controller using LOLIMOT State Space Representation	73
5.3	Model Simulation and Analysis of the Results	75
6	Conclusion	77
	Bibliography	79
A	Definition of System Parameters	81
A.0.1	LOLIMOT Pseudocode Algorithm	82

List of Figures

2.1	Schematic representation of the black-box block model for the LOLIMOT loading bridge model	9
2.2	Network structure of a static local linear neuro-fuzzy model with M neurons for p inputs	10
2.3	Parallel system identification structure for minimizing the output error	11
2.4	Division of the input space into cuboids and placement of weighting functions	19
2.5	Four iterations of the tree structure of the LOLIMOT algorithm . . .	20
2.6	NRMSE vs nbpart	21
2.7	Schematic representation of a standard control loop.	27
3.1	Schematic representation of the loading bridge	36
3.2	Schematic representation of the loading bridge with the three target variables	37
3.3	Cross-sectional view of the subsystems according to	38
3.4	Graphical representation of the inputs of the loading bridge	44
3.5	Graphical representation of nonlinear model outputs compared to the quasi-linear model	48
3.6	Block diagram of the linear state space representation of the system .	49
3.7	Graphical representation of the nonlinear mathematical model compared to the linear model	50
3.8	Block diagram of the observer in state space representation	51
3.9	Graphical representation of LQR observer compared to the nonlinear mathematical model	52
3.10	Block diagram of the observer-based state controller	53
4.1	Graphical representation of the input and output signals of a nonlinear model	56
4.2	Graphical representation of the training and validation data of the neuro-fuzzy algorithm	57
4.3	Representation of the block diagram of system identification	61
4.4	Results of four iterations of the LOLIMOT algorithm for carriage position, rope angle and rope length	62
4.5	Graphical representation of the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm for carriage position, rope angle and rope length in comparison to the nonlinear model	63
4.6	NRMSE and the quality measures of four local linear models	64
4.7	Comparison of the quality measure results of all models	64
4.8	Block diagram of the state space representation of the LOLIMOT model	69

5.1	Block diagram of the observer of the LOLIMOT model	72
5.2	Block diagram of the observer-based state controller of the LOLIMOT model	74
5.3	Graphical representation of the nonlinear model compared to all models as well as the local linear model (LOLIMOT) outputs	74
5.4	Graphical representation of the nonlinear model compared to all models as well as the local linear model (LOLIMOT) outputs	75

List of Tables

3.1	Results of the quality measures of the quasi-linear model compared to the nonlinear model	47
3.2	Quality measures of the linear model compared to the nonlinear model	50
3.3	The quality measures of the LQR observer model compared to the nonlinear model for $x_{5AP} = 0.2m$	52
3.4	Control performance of the LQR observer-based state controller model for $x_{5AP} = 0.2m$	54
4.1	Quality Measures and NRMSE results of the local linear model	63
A.1	System parameters for the carriage	81
A.2	System parameters for the drum	81
A.3	System parameters for the weight	81

1 Introduction

Overhead cranes are widely used in industry, including in the automotive, airport, and heavy civil engineering sectors. This equipment plays a key role in lifting and transporting heavy loads such as containers, construction blocks, railway wagons, turbines, and liquid tanks. They operate according to the physical principles of conventional electric machines and pendulum systems. Today, overhead cranes consist of massive structures capable of lifting loads weighing thousands of tons. Ideally, they should guarantee positioning accuracy, transport speed, and robustness against disturbances and uncertainties.

The development of control systems for overhead cranes is of great importance due to their numerous applications and the significant advantages over manual operation in terms of stability and robustness. In this thesis, the most important nonlinear dynamics of overhead cranes are represented using a compact local model network, also known as a "local neuro-fuzzy model" or "Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model" [Cla20, S.25], which can be extended with a neuro-fuzzy state-space model. The neuro-fuzzy model supports the design of a neuro-fuzzy dynamic controller through parallel distributed compensation. A feasibility problem with conservative linear matrix inequalities is formulated such that a solution can be found using Lyapunov stability in the closed-loop system with constrained inputs, fast positioning of the support trolley, and suppression of load oscillations. The proposed neuro-fuzzy control for overhead cranes has proven to be effective and robust, enabling smooth movement of loads even after collisions. Continuous and smooth input signals avoid actuator saturation and tend to extend the service life of overhead cranes.

Overhead cranes are characterized by a mobile platform that moves along elevated rails. A steel rope is attached to the underside of the platform and serves to lift the load. Such a rope is equipped with a hook at its lowest point so that the load can be attached and transported. A major operational challenge is the smoothness with which the load must be moved to a reference point. Acceleration, deceleration, and disturbances along the path should not cause excessive oscillations for safety reasons and to avoid potential economic losses. Only the trolley movement can be controlled directly, while the swing angle of the load is not directly accessible. An effective feedback control system is therefore urgently recommended so that the trolley reaches the reference or follows a trajectory while the swing angle remains close to the vertical.

Control design methods for overhead cranes are very often based on nonlinear or linearized single-pendulum models under the assumption of sufficiently small swing angles. In this context, MIMO systems are frequently used, which contain several manipulated variables (input variables) and measured variables (output variables). The controller design for MIMO systems should consider all input-output combinations simultaneously [DEH20]. However, several factors can cause the oscillation amplitudes to exceed the small-angle assumption, because the dynamics

of the overhead crane cannot be fully linearized. Furthermore, overhead cranes often operate under irregular extreme conditions, are exposed to strong air currents, or are mounted on ships where many external disturbances are present, which can lead to unexpected collisions. Additional unmodeled uncertainties are difficult to describe with precise mathematical expressions. These include aging of the overhead crane, wear, variations in operating conditions, and disturbances. The performance of the control system can deteriorate because the safe tolerance range tends to be small.

When the model and the neuro-fuzzy controller have the same antecedent membership functions, such a control scheme is referred to as parallel distributed compensation (PDC). A stable closed-loop system can be achieved by applying the direct Lyapunov method and using linear matrix inequalities (LMIs) [Deh+22, S. 4]. If a feasible solution for an LMI can be found, the stability of the closed-loop system is theoretically guaranteed. In the present master thesis, sector nonlinearity and local approximation in fuzzy representation spaces are used to obtain a compact neuro-fuzzy model and a less conservative LMI problem. The actuator saturation effect is addressed by appending additional inequalities to the LMI to limit the control input.

This work consists of six chapters. After the introduction, the second chapter presents all the basic information on control topics used in our model design. The third section explains all the basic information about the overhead crane system step by step, including linearization and the state-space representation of a controller. The fourth chapter explains how a black-box model is prepared using the LOLIMOT algorithm. The fifth chapter deals with the design of an observer-based state feedback controller. All results from MATLAB/Simulink models are presented graphically here. The sixth chapter is the conclusion.

2 Basics

In this chapter, all basic concepts required for local linear modeling are explained. These are fundamental methods required for the identification of dynamic systems. Because the system is a nonlinear and dynamic multibody system. Furthermore, the method used for mathematical modeling will be the black-box model. This modeling is briefly described here and explained in detail in Chapter 4. A basic coupling of control engineering with plants such as the loading bridge requires consideration of signal and measurement technology standards, which are essential for the use of various control methods. To be able to control, the signals must be acquired and measured. Here, the basic control engineering instruments that are needed are briefly described. A loading bridge is a dynamic, nonlinear multibody system.

2.1 System Description

Models of real systems are of fundamental importance in almost all disciplines. Models can be useful for system analysis, i.e., to gain a better understanding of the system. Models enable the prediction or simulation of a system's behavior. In engineering, models are needed for the design of new processes and for the analysis of existing processes. Advanced techniques for controller design, optimization, monitoring, fault detection, and diagnosis components are also based on process models. Before considering the development of a nonlinear model, a linear model should be considered first. If the linear model does not provide satisfactory performance, one possible explanation, among many others, is a significantly nonlinear behavior of the process. Whether this is actually the case can be investigated by a careful comparison between the process and the linear model and/or by a nonlinearity test. For example, step responses can reveal operating point-dependent behavior. A good strategy to avoid this undesirable effect is to use a nonlinear model architecture that contains a linear model as a special case. Examples of such models are polynomials that gradually simplify to a linear model or local linear neuro-fuzzy models that simplify to a linear model when the number of neurons/rules equals one. For other nonlinear model architectures, it can be advantageous to create a linear model in parallel. The total model output is thus the sum of the linear and nonlinear model parts. This strategy is very appealing because it ensures that the overall nonlinear model performs better than the linear model [Nel01, S. 2]. Nonlinear system identification for dynamic systems is explained in detail in Section 4.1.

2.1.1 Nonlinear State Space Representation

The machine that is the subject of our research is a widely used machine with dynamic system properties. To model this system mathematically, a mathematical model must first be created that contains the properties of the system, and our next goal is to obtain a black-box model by using the input and output signals obtained from the model.

With this model, an attempt is made to realize it using Simulink-Matlab. Since our system is a dynamic multibody system, an equation of motion must be constructed to obtain the motion of a system so that the system cannot be described mathematically. For this purpose, Lagrange equations are used, which are used in the identification of dynamic multibody systems. Using the Lagrange equation, n number of equations with n independent motion possibilities can be created.

2.1.2 Linearization

When determining the manipulated variable for a real system, real systems are nonlinear. The nonlinear dynamic system is determined using the Lagrange equation of motion. The derivation of the desired manipulated variables from the state space model takes place. In most cases, real systems have one or more nonlinear differential equations or a nonlinear state space model. This is described in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= f(x(t), u(t)) \\ y(t) &= g(x(t), u(t)) \\ x(0) &= x_0 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

The vector function is represented as f . The detailed representation of the state equation of the model is as follows Equation (2.1)

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{x}_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, u) \\ f_2(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, u) \\ \vdots \\ f_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, u) \end{pmatrix}$$

For reasons of clarity, the specification of the time dependence of all signals has been omitted. Linear models are used in control engineering, despite the nonlinear character of the real world. This control is particularly applied when a system is to be kept at a given operating point despite the influence of external disturbances. The decision to use linear models is then very easy to justify. If the control works, the system remains in the vicinity of the operating point, and this is sufficient if the

model describes the system motion around this operating point. For small deviations, the nonlinear model can be used for linearization. Thus, the determination of an operating point is the starting point for linearization. The variables x, u, y describe the operating point that satisfies the conditions

$$0 = f(\bar{x}, \bar{u}) \quad (2.2)$$

$$y = g(\bar{x}, \bar{u}) \quad (2.3)$$

Under the first condition, the state x settles, which represents a steady state of the system that establishes itself at the input variable $u(t) = u$. The second condition specifies that in this steady state, the output variable has the value $y(t) = \bar{y}$. The parameters $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ in the linearized model are to represent the deviations of these variables from the specified operating point values \bar{x}, \bar{u} and \bar{y} instead of the original variables $x(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta x(t) &= x(t) - \bar{x} \\ \delta u(t) &= u(t) - \bar{u} \\ \delta y(t) &= y(t) - \bar{y} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

From Equation (2.1) and Equation (2.4) we obtain

$$\frac{d\delta x(t)}{dt} = \dot{x}(t)$$

and

$$\frac{d\delta x(t)}{dt} = f\left(\bar{x} + \delta x(t), \bar{u} + \delta u(t)\right).$$

If the vector function f is expanded into a Taylor series around the operating point (\bar{u}, \bar{x}) , we obtain

$$\frac{d\delta x(t)}{dt} = f\left(\bar{x}, \bar{u}\right) + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} \cdot \delta x(t) + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}\right)_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} \cdot \delta u(t) + r(\delta x, \delta u)$$

where the remainder of the Taylor series is represented by $r(\delta x, \delta u)$ and the first summand on the right-hand side is zero due to the condition Equation (2.2). The application of this procedure assumes that the function f (and for the linearization of the output equation the function g) is differentiable at the operating point.

$\delta x(t)$ and $\delta u(t)$ are small in magnitude if the system moves in the near vicinity of the given operating point, and thus the remainder can be neglected compared to the first-order terms. The derivatives of a vector with respect to a vector or a scalar are described by the two differential quotients and consequently represent a matrix or a vector, which are denoted by A or b , respectively:

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial x_n} \end{pmatrix}_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} = A \quad (2.5)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}\right)_{x=\bar{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial u} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial u} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_n}{\partial u} \end{pmatrix}_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} = b \quad (2.6)$$

The matrix Equation (2.5) is called the Jacobian or functional matrix. This yields the linear relationship

$$\frac{d\delta x(t)}{dt} \approx A\delta x(t) + b\delta u(t), \delta x(0) = x(0) - \bar{x}$$

In control engineering, calculations are often performed using deviations from the operating point instead of the absolute values of the signals, therefore the delta before the signals is omitted and the rounding symbol is replaced by an equal sign:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = Ax(t) + bu(t), x(0) = x(0) - \bar{x} \quad (2.7)$$

When evaluating and interpreting the results obtained from this model, this simplified notation must be considered and recalled. The nonlinear output equation of the model can be linearized in the same way, where

$$\delta y(t) \approx c^T \delta x(t) + d\delta u(t)$$

or

$$y(t) = c^T x(t) + du(t) \quad (2.8)$$

with

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial x}\right)_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} = c^T \quad (2.9)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial u}\right)_{x=\bar{x}, u=\bar{u}} = d \quad (2.10)$$

results. Equation (2.7), Equation (2.9) with the matrices and vectors from Equation (2.6), Equation (2.7), Equation (2.10) and Equation (2.11) represent the linearized state space model, Linearized model:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= Ax(t) + bu(t) \\ x(0) &= x(0) - \bar{x} \\ y(t) &= c^T x(t) + du(t) \end{aligned}$$

which describes the motion of the nonlinear system Equation (2.1) around the operating point $(\bar{u}, \bar{x}, \bar{y})$, where according to the explanations, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ denote the deviations of the input and output from the operating point values \bar{u} and \bar{y} , respectively [Lun14, S. 105-108].

2.2 System Identification

Before deciding on a model, it must be examined why a model is necessary. Our system is a continuous system and therefore, as with real systems, there are infinitely many data points ($N \rightarrow \infty$). It is really difficult to realize this amount of data on a computer, especially since they are mostly nonlinear. To understand the difference between continuous systems and discrete systems, the continuous and cascading systems are therefore examined in the next chapter (see Chapter 2.5). Subsequently, the differences and advantages of the various structures of white-box, gray-box, and black-box models are explained in order to select a suitable model structure for the dynamic system. The goal is to create and understand why a black-box model is needed. For a better understanding, the structures of other models are also considered.

Black-Box, Gray-Box and White-Box Models

The amount of prior knowledge about the system structure that flows into the modeling is another distinguishing criterion when introducing models for dynamic systems. The distinction lies on a scale between black (so-called black-box models) and white (white-box models), with gray-box models lying between black-box models and white-box models. A distinction must be made as to how the model structure, i.e., the equation that describes the behavior of the system, determines the parameters appearing in these equations. The model structure of white-box models is determined from known, e.g., physical laws or from physical approaches.

The parameters are known or specified by the design. Thus, no measurement or experiments on the system are required to determine the entire model. [BU16] Black-box models are developed by measuring the system input and output data and fitting a mathematical function to the data. No understanding of the system physics is required to develop black-box models. Compared to physics-based models, black-box models have high accuracy despite poor generalization capabilities. A model structure was constructed to describe the nonlinear dynamics. This is the nonlinear black-box structure for the dynamic system. The view of nonlinear anatomies can be considered as a concatenation of the structures of the observed data onto a regression vector and the nonlinear structures of the regressor space onto the output space. For this, understanding the difference between black-box models, gray-box models, and white-box models is important. The main focus of research on black-box model modeling methods is currently on the precise realization of the structural relationship between inputs and outputs and thus on the precise realization of the implicit relationship. Many scholars have adopted a variety of methods for creating the black-box model to solve specific technical problems. These include, for example, the following models: the transfer function model (TF), the autoaggressive public model (ARX), the output error model (OE), and the state space model (SS). Nevertheless, research on the relationship between inputs and outputs is lacking. System variables that have a representative meaning are introduced into the black-box model. These variables represent both input and output variables (self-coupling). However, when calculating the black-box model, the actual input variable is not included. To be able to observe the operation of the system, a "virtual" variable exists in the system, which can generate the output as an analysis parameter. [CSL20, S. 1].

In gray-box models, the model equations are at least partially determined from known laws or other, e.g., physically motivated considerations, and yet the parameters appearing in the model equations are at least partially unknown. In black-box models, these unknown parameters are determined from measured input and output data via experimental system identification. Depending on the extent of the prior knowledge incorporated, different shades of gray can be assigned to the models. This allows an introduction on a scale from white to black. This classification is arbitrary to a certain extent [Cla20].

The following block diagram is prepared for the loading bridge of the black-box model. The main goal is to obtain expected results using input and output measurement data, by working with real measurement data with two inputs and three outputs or with a nonlinear mathematical model without complicated physical equations (see Chapter 3.3.1)

Here, the input signals of our black-box model, u_1 stands for carriage drive force and u_2 for drum drive force. Our output signals are y_1 carriage position, y_2 rope angle, and y_3 stands for rope length. In our next topic, Local Model Network, which was selected as a black-box model, it will be explained in more detail how each output

Figure 2.1 Schematic representation of the black-box block model for the LOLIMOT loading bridge model

signal is obtained.

2.3 Local Model Networks

Local model networks, also known as local neuro-fuzzy models or Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy models, can be interpreted as operating point or spatially correlated, weighted, and stacked input models. Therefore, the global model is formed by successive transformations of the local model.

This chapter covers the basics of modeling with local model networks. The works of Nelles, Hartmann, and Schröder are to be mentioned as relevant sources. System identification is an important topic of current work, as efficient and high-quality modeling is the foundation of any model-based control engineering approach. The focus is on experimental modeling, which is performed using neural, network-based adaptive algorithms. Local model networks represent a special subclass of neural networks that are suitable for approximating static structures and are particularly suitable for identifying nonlinear dynamic systems [Cla20, S. 25]. To fully understand our system, you can better inform yourself about neural networks and neuro-fuzzy systems using these [RP96b], [Stu99], [H+15] resources.

The focus is on locally linear models and axis-orthogonal partitioning, which allows interpretation with one-dimensional fuzzy membership functions. If the partitions are not axis-orthogonal, then the fuzzy interpretation becomes very difficult and unintuitive with multidimensional membership functions. This is what most people experience when they lose the fuzzy edge. Local linear modeling methods are based on a divide-and-conquer strategy. A complex modeling problem is broken down into several smaller and thus simpler subproblems that are solved (almost) independently by identifying simple models (e.g., linear models). The most important factor for the success of this approach is the partitioning strategy of the original complex problem. Therefore, the properties of a locally linear neuro-fuzzy model critically depend on

the construction algorithm used to implement a specific partitioning strategy [Nel20, S.393].

2.3.1 Mathematical Formulation of Local Model Networks

As already mentioned, local model networks represent networks of local superposition and weighted models, which consist of many neurons, each consisting of a local model and an associated nonlinear weighting function, see Fig 2.2. As a model structure of the LM, for example, polynomial models with different polynomial degrees can be used. Locally linear model structures are of particular interest because parameter optimization of the LM is particularly easy to implement here. Furthermore, the locally linear properties of the model can be used for stability analyses. However, there are also many applications where high-degree polynomials have produced good results. A very interesting approach is one that adaptively adjusts the complexity of the LM during structure optimization. In the present work, given the mentioned advantages, locally linear models are used [Cla20, S. 26].

Figure 2.2 Network structure of a static local linear neuro-fuzzy model with M neurons for p inputs according to [Cla20, S. 27]

The model output $y \in R$ is defined using LLM according to Fig 2.2 as

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\sum_{j=0}^n w_{ij} \cdot u_j \right) \cdot \Phi_i(u) \quad (2.11)$$

where M is the number of LLMs, m is the number of inputs of the LMN and $w_{ij} \in R$ are the respective polynomial coefficients of the LLMs with running indices $i = 1 \dots M$ and $j = 0 \dots m$. Each LLM has its individual weighting function $\Phi_i(u)$, which depends on the input vector u . The input vector combines all inputs u_j . The first element is defined as $u_0 = 1$, so that the first parameters w_{i0} are to be interpreted as constants of the transfer function [Cla20, S. 26].

The output of the i -th LLM \hat{y}_i can also be defined in vector form using the parameter vector θ_i

$$\hat{y}_i = u^T \cdot \theta_i \quad (2.12)$$

As already mentioned, local model networks are suitable for approximating static and dynamic models. To identify dynamic models, the so-called parallel identification structure is used in the present work.

Figure 2.3 Parallel system identification structure for minimizing the output error according to [Cla20, S. 28]

According to Figure(2.3), although the measured process inputs $u(k)$ with the number m of inputs as well as the approximated model output $\hat{y}(k)$ are used as input variables of the model network. The discrete-time transition function of a dynamic LLM is defined as

$$A_i(z^{-1}) y_i(k) = B_i(z^{-1}) u(k) + c_i \quad (2.13)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} A_i(z^{-1}) &= 1 + a_{i_1}z^{-1} + a_{i_2}z^{-2} + \dots + a_{i_{n_a}}z^{-n_{out}} \\ B_i(z^{-1}) &= b_{i_1}z^{-1} + b_{i_2}z^{-2} + \dots + b_{i_{n_b}}z^{-n_{in}} \end{aligned}$$

Here c_i is the constant term of the transfer function of an LLM. The index k defines the measurement time and is defined as a positive integer quantity in the present work. Furthermore, it is specified that the measurement is carried out with a constant sampling time T . The process inputs are delayed to the respective dynamic orders n_{in} . The dynamic orders of the inputs define the degree of the input polynomial of the transfer function and are parameters that must be optimized as part of the process identification. Additionally, the output of the model is delayed up to a defined degree n_{out} . The model output $y_i(k)$ at time k is defined according to equation (2.14) as

$$z(k) = (u(k-1) \dots u(k-n_{in}) - y(k-1) \dots - y(k-n_{out}))^T \quad (2.14)$$

for the parameter vector θ_i to be optimized of a dynamic LLM, accordingly

$$\theta_i = (b_{i_1} \dots b_{i_{n_{in}}} \quad a_{i_1} \dots a_{i_{n_{out}}} \quad c_i)^T \quad (2.15)$$

Equation 4.11 can be defined accordingly in vector notation as

$$\hat{y}(k) = z^T(k) \cdot \theta_i \quad (2.16)$$

with the vector

$$z(k) = (u(k-1) \dots U(k-n_{in}) - y(k-1) \dots - y(k-n_{out}))^T \quad (2.17)$$

The parameter vector θ_i is composed of the polynomial coefficients of the model input and output variables and a constant term with $nt = m \cdot n_{in} + n_{out} + 1$. By setting the constant parameter c to zero, the stability analysis of the LLMs proves particularly simple. In most cases, however, this leads to a decrease in model accuracy, which must be considered during modeling. Here, by forming the controller normal form based on the polynomial coefficients a_{ij} , the system matrix A , the stability properties of the individual LLMs can be efficiently investigated cf. Section (3.2.3). [CLA20b]. The optimization of the parameters of the local linear network is the main goal of identifying a dynamic system. The error $e(k) = y(k) - \hat{y}(k)$ should minimize the existing measurement for the N measurement point. With the help of structure optimization, the optimal parameter vectors θ_i of all LLMs and the respective weighting functions Φ_i must be considered and thereby iteratively divide the input space axis-orthogonally or axis-obliquely.

The weighting function is represented as follows

$$\Phi_i(u) = \frac{\mu_i(u)}{\sum_{j=1}^M \mu_j(u)} \quad (2.18)$$

with

$$\mu_i(u) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{(u_1 - c_{i1})^2}{\sigma_{i1}^2} + \dots + \frac{(u_p - c_{ip})^2}{\sigma_{ip}^2}\right)\right) \quad (2.19)$$

$$\mu_i(u) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\frac{(u_1 - c_{i1})^2}{\sigma_{i1}^2}\right) \dots \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\frac{(u_p - c_{ip})^2}{\sigma_{ip}^2}\right)$$

The optimizers use different loss functions, which are defined in the next step. Using a local loss function see (Section 2.3.6), it is approximated for N points [Nel20, S.396]. The normalized Gaussian validity functions depend on the center coordinates c_{ij} and the dimension of the individual standard deviations σ_{ij} . The parameters represent the hidden layer parameters of the neural network and are therefore nonlinear. The optimization of this data is discussed in Sec. 2.3.2. The validity functions are also called activation functions because they weight the activity of the LLMs or, considering the basis function formulation of equation (2.14) in Sec. 2.3.1, the interpolation functions or weighting functions [Nel20, S. 396].

2.3.2 Local Linear Model Trees - LOLIMOT-

LOLIMOT (Local Linear Model Trees) is an incremental tree construction algorithm that partitions the input space by axis-orthogonal divisions. In each iteration, a new rule or a local linear model (LLM) is added to the model. Thus, LOLIMOT belongs to the class of *incremental* or *growing* algorithms. It implements a heuristic search for the rule premise structure and avoids time-consuming, nonlinear optimization. In each iteration of the algorithm, the validity functions corresponding to the actual partitioning of the input space are calculated, as shown in Figure 2.2 [Nel20, S. 421]. In recent years, the focus has shifted from linear system identification to nonlinear system identification methods, driven by the need to capture inherent nonlinear effects of real systems. This paper considers the identification of nonlinear state space systems. For this type of problem, it has been shown that errors due to inadequate modeling of nonlinear behavior outweigh the error due to inappropriate noise models by using a nonlinear distortion analysis. Therefore, process noise is not considered, but rather the focus is on developing a robust algorithm for identifying deterministic, nonlinear state-space models [SMN19a, S. 1]

Procedure of the LOLIMOT Algorithm

- 1. Start with the initial model:**

The validity function is first constructed with which the initial partitioning of the input space and the local model parameters are approximated. If no input space partitioning is available, start with a local signal model for the entire input region.
- 2. Find the worst local model:**

Calculate the local loss function for each local model and find the local model with the worst performance.
- 3. Check all divisions:**

Divide the worst local model orthogonally in each of the 0 dimensions of the z-space and approximate two new local models. Calculate the loss function for each global model structure.
- 4. Find the best division:**

Select the best of all p-splits according to the quality criterion used and update the structure.
- 5. Find all possible fusion partners:**

Only adjoint Gaussians of adjacent validity regions may be merged. This restriction guarantees that the local characteristic of each local model and its region is preserved. This ensures good interpretability of the local model structure.
- 6. Check all fusion partners:**

Combine all fusion partners by summing their validity functions: $\Phi_z(ij) = \Phi_z(i) + \Phi_z(j)$. Note that it does not matter whether the normalized or unnormalized Gaussian functions are added, since the sum of all Gaussian functions in the denominator used for normalization is the same. Approximate the local models for the new validity spaces and calculate the loss function for each global model structure.
- 7. Find the best merging result:**

Select the best merging options with respect to the quality criterion used.

8. **Improvement test:**

Only global models of the same complexity can be meaningfully compared. Therefore, the merged model structure is needed before the best orthogonal division. Only if the merging leads to an improvement in quality, the structure is updated accordingly.

9. **Convergence test:**

If one of the termination criteria, such as a threshold for the training error or the number of local models, is reached, training is terminated and proceed to step 2.

The algorithm can switch between two complexity levels by performing several merging and splitting operations in sequence. This leads to a redistribution of the validity spaces without increasing the number of local models [Nel01, S. 552].

2.3.3 Determination of Dynamic Orders of the Model

Now the dynamic orders of the system have been determined so that an adequate result of the Local Model Network (LOLIMOT) algorithm is possible. The selection of the dynamic order can be very complicated, therefore the trial and error method was used. In this work, the loading bridge has two inputs, drum force and carriage force, and three outputs, carriage position, rope angle, and rope length. Nelles' book 2001 [Nel01, S.562] explained very clearly how to solve the problem of selecting dynamic orders.

If the external dynamics approach is chosen, the problem of order determination is basically equivalent to determining the relevant inputs for the function $\hat{y}(\cdot)$ in (2.19). Although the previous input signal $u(k-i)$ and output signal $y(k-i)$ can formally be considered as separate inputs for the function $\hat{y}(\cdot)$, they possess certain properties that make order determination a much more difficult problem than selecting physically different inputs. For example, $y(k-1)$ and $y(k-2)$ are typically strongly correlated (indicating redundancy) but may still both be relevant. So far, no order determination procedure has been developed that fully considers the special properties resulting from the external dynamics approach.

The problem of order determination for nonlinear dynamic systems is still not satisfactorily solved. Surprisingly, very little research seems to be devoted to this important area. It is common practice to select the dynamic order of the model through a combination of trial and error and prior knowledge about the process (if available). Some basic observations can support this procedure. Obviously, if oscillatory behavior is observed, the process must be at least second order. Step responses can be examined at some operating points and linear order determination methods applied. This may allow an approximate order determination of the nonlinear

process. However, this is a tedious procedure, and reliable automatic data based on higher-order correlations are proposed. However, these approaches are merely model validation tools, where a model with a specific order must first be created and specified, which information may be missing [Nel01, S. 574–576]. In this work, the trial-and-error method was used. One can also use the Liptische index method. For this, the appropriate input order can be found by formulating different input and output variations. Then a Liptische index diagram can also be produced. Further information can be found in the following source [Nel01, P.576]. In Fig. 4.1, the input signals decided for the loading bridge using the trial-and-error method are graphically represented.

2.3.4 Parameter Optimization

The structure of LOLIMOT is assumed to be fixed. The centers and standard deviations of the M local, linear submodels (LLM) are thus given. The parameters of the entire local, linear models are approximated separately using the weighted least-squares method. By using linear optimization methods, parameter optimization is very fast. It always leads to the global minimum of the loss function. With the data matrix X (the k th row contains the measure vector $x(k) = [x_1(k) \ x_2(k) \ \dots \ x_n(k)]$), the diagonal weighting matrix Q_i (the element q_{kk}) is the value of the i th weighting function at the point $x(k)$ and the vector of reference values y , the optimal parameter vector w_i of the i th local, linear model is calculated as

$$w_i = (X^T \cdot Q_i \cdot X)^{-1} \cdot X^T \cdot Q_i \cdot y \quad (2.20)$$

This means that for the approximation of a local, linear model, the data are weighted according to their belonging to exactly this model. Data points that are further away in the input space are not considered. Data points near the center of the model's weighting region are heavily weighted. The centers can be interpreted as operating points for the local, linear models. Using (Equation 2.20), the $n + 1$ parameters are calculated separately for all local, linear models. This type of approximation is called local approximation because the influence of the other models is not considered when calculating the parameters of one model. Since the weighting functions overlap each other, each parameter of each model influences the LOLIMOT output (see (Chapter 2.3.1) Equation 2.14). When locally approximating the model parameters, all influences of other models are neglected. The error that arises as a result is called interpolation error. The overlap of the weighting functions and thus the interpolation error is equal to 0 when switching sharply between the models ($\sigma = 0$). As the overlap increases, the interpolation error increases steadily. A global approximation set could avoid interpolation errors by calculating the parameters of all M local, linear models in a system of equations. That is, an $M \cdot (n+1)$ dimensional matrix must be inverted instead of the only $(n+1)$ -dimensional matrix in (Equations

2.20). The local parameter approximation according to (Equations 2.20) has important advantages over a global approximation. Since each model is approximated individually, the computational effort increases only with $O(M)$, i.e., linearly, as the number of local, linear models increases. Because of the cubic complexity of matrix inversion, the global approximation results in $O(M^3)$. Local approximation is already much faster than global at $M = 2$, and this effect increases strongly with increasing complexity.

Local approximation is dominant in terms of approximation quality despite interpolation errors when data is corrupted. This is due to the lower variance of the locally approximated parameters. This can be illustrated as follows. When approximating with a corrupted training dataset, the parameters will not reach their optimal value due to the noise. Therefore, the expected loss function for new test data measured independently of the training data is proportional to $1 + (\text{number of parameters}) / (\text{number of training data values})$. For global approximation of parameters, the expected loss function is thus proportional to

$$1 + \frac{M \cdot (n + 1)}{N} \quad (2.21)$$

with N = number of training data, M = number of local, linear models and n = input space dimension. For local approximation, this proportionality factor is far smaller for practical cases and lies between (Equations 4.2) and (Equations 4.3).

$$1 + \frac{n + 1}{N} \quad (2.22)$$

the proportionality factor in (Equations 4.3) is not achievable because not all N training points are evaluated equally for local approximation. Due to the weighting, the effective number of training data, depending on the overlap of the weighting functions, is smaller than N . In the extreme case of sharp switching between local, linear models ($\sigma = 0$), on average only N/M instead of N data points would be available for each model in (Equations 4.3) and local approximation would lose this advantage. For practically meaningful values of σ , however, local approximation results in a significantly reduced approximation variance. This is paid for in terms of the bias-variance dilemma with a slightly increased bias due to interpolation errors. For all examples tested so far, the variance reduction far outweighed the bias increase, so that local compared to global approximation leads to a smaller loss function (calculated with the test data).

Local approximation has thus led to a regularization effect and thereby reduces the danger of overfitting. [Nel96]

2.3.5 Structure Optimization

So far, the description of parameter optimization has assumed a given structure. Next, the tree construction algorithm for optimizing the LOLIMOT structure is presented. It is based on ideas of known tree construction methods such as basis function trees, CART (classification and regression trees), and MARS (multivariate adaptive regression splines).

The LOLIMOT algorithm divides the input space of the function U_p into hypercuboids. The center c of the weighting function is placed in the middle of the hypercuboid. The standard deviation σ is chosen in each spatial direction proportional to the extent of the hypercuboid. Thus, the size of the validity region of a local, linear model is determined by the volume of the associated hypercuboid. These structures are shown in Fig. 2.4 for the two-dimensional case. The circles and ellipses correspond to the contour lines of the still unnormalized Gaussian bells. In Fig. 2.4, it can be seen that it is possible that a model is responsible for all amplitude ranges at input (u_2) , but only for a small amplitude range at another input (u_1) .

The construction of the hypercuboids follows the algorithm below Fig.2.5a and 2.5b :

1. Place the 1st hypercuboid so that it just encloses all data points. Approximate a global linear model $y = w_0 + w_1x_1 + \dots + w_nx_n$
2. For all input dimensions $j = 1 \dots n$:
 - (a) Divide the hypercuboid into two halves along dimension j .
 - (b) Place a weighting function in both new hypercuboids.
 - (c) Approximate the parameters of the local, linear models for both halves according to (6).
 - (d) Calculate the output error of the LOLIMOT model according to (4) and (5).
3. Determine which of the above n cuts yields the smallest output error.
4. Perform this cut. Use the weighting functions from 2b) and the parameters from 2c).
5. Calculate local error measures for each local, linear model by weighting the output error from 2d) with the associated weighting functions.
6. Select the hypercuboid with the largest local loss function for the next division.
7. If the termination criterion is not met, then go to step 2.
8. Algorithm has converged.

Figure 2.4 Division of the input space into cuboids and placement of weighting functions according to [Nel96]

9. Stop.

In each iteration, the worst submodel is separated into two submodels. This adapts the local complexity of the model depending on the local complexity of the function to be approximated. Thus, models are only refined and consequently additional parameters are approximated where necessary.

In step 2, the division of the local, linear model is tested in all spatial directions. Then the division with the greatest error reduction is selected. It is important that due to the normalization, the division of one model into two submodels also results in minimal changes in the weighting functions of the other local, linear models. Accordingly, the parameters of all submodels would have to be re-approximated. However, because the changes are negligibly small (in the percent range), this step is omitted in favor of increased efficiency.

Starting from a global model, which is then gradually refined, is a desirable property of this method. On the one hand, the degree of improvement in each iteration gives the user an indication for the choice of optimal model complexity. On the other hand, this ensures that the number of parameters only increases linearly with the input dimension. The above LOLIMOT algorithm is specifically adapted for the application of identifying dynamic systems. Parameter optimization is based on the equation error (NARX) in order to use fast, linear approximation methods. However, structure optimization is based on the output error (NEO) to avoid any possible error propagation due to feedback. At the same time, the output error calculation tests the generalization quality, because due to the feedback, the approximated values sometimes present new input signals at the LOLIMOT input. This allows overfitting to be detected and prevented.

Figure 2.5 Four iterations of the tree structure of the LOLIMOT algorithm according to [Nel96]

Fig. 2.5A shows four iterations for a two-dimensional input space of this LOLIMOT algorithm, which can be represented in a tree structure as in Fig. 2.5B. Fig. 2.6 shows a typical progression of the output error over these four iterations (a)-(d). The error value at four iterations shows the quality measure (SSQ) of the linear model. This is optimized through each iteration [Nel96].

2.3.6 Local Approximation

Note: Local approximations are very important for determining bad local linear models so that algorithms can continue with the partitioning.

The idea of the local approximation theorem is to treat the optimization of the rule-following parameters as individual problems. The parameters for each local linear model are approximated separately, neglecting the interactions between the

Figure 2.6 Representation of quality measures (SSQ) and NRMSE for five iterations of the LOLIMOT algorithm

local models. As discussed below, this increases the bias error of the model. The motivation for this approach arises from the case $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, in which no interaction takes place between the different local models. The output of the model for given inputs u is determined exclusively by a single local linear model, while all others are inactive. In this case, the local approximation theorem exactly matches the global one. When σ is increased, the interaction between neighboring local models grows and the error caused by neglecting them increases.

Instead of approximating all $n = M(p+1)$ parameters simultaneously, as is the case with the global approach, M separate local approximations are performed for the $p + 1$ parameters of each local linear model. The parameter vector for each of these $i = 1, \dots, M$ approximations is

$$w_i = [w_{i0} \ w_{i1} \ \dots \ w_{ip}]^T \quad (2.23)$$

the corresponding regression matrices are

$$x_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & u_1(1) & u_2(1) & \dots & u_p(1) \\ 1 & u_1(2) & u_2(2) & \dots & u_p(2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ 1 & u_1(N) & u_2(N) & \dots & u_p(N) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.24)$$

Note that here the regression matrices of all local linear models $i = 1, \dots, M$ are identical, since the entries of X_i do not depend on i . However, as discussed in Sec. 14.3, this can be generalized to local models of different structure; therefore, it is helpful to keep the index i in X_i . A local linear model with output $y_i = [y_i(1) \ y_i(2) \ \dots \ y_i(N)]$

$$\hat{y}_i = X_i \cdot w_i \quad (2.25)$$

holds only in the region where the associated validity function Φ_i is close to 1. This will be the case near the center of Φ_i . Data in this region are very relevant for the approximation of w_i . As the validity function decreases, the data become less relevant for the approximation of w_i and more relevant for the approximation of the neighboring models. Consequently, it is straightforward to apply a weighted least squares optimization, where the weighting factors are given by the validity function values, i.e.,

$$I = \sum_{j=1}^N \Phi_i(\underline{u}(j)) e^2(j) \rightarrow \min_{\underline{w}_i} \quad (2.26)$$

where $e(j) = y(j) - \hat{y}(j)$ represents the model errors for the data sample $[u(j), y(j)]$. For the extreme case $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, $\Phi(u(j))$ is either 0 or 1, i.e., only a subset of the data is used for the approximation of w_i . For $\sigma > 0$, all data samples are used for approximation, but those whose validity value is close to 0 are practically ignored. With the following diagonal $N \times N$ weighting matrix

$$x_i = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_i(\underline{u}(1)) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \Phi_i(\underline{u}(2)) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \Phi_i(\underline{u}(N)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.27)$$

the weighted LS solution for the parameters of rule sequence i is given by (for $N \Rightarrow p + 1$)

$$w_i = (X_i^T Q_i X_i)^{-1} X_i^T Q_i y \quad (2.28)$$

this approximation must be computed successively for all $i = 1 \dots M$ local linear models [Nel20, S. 407–410].

2.3.7 Global Approximation

Note: Global approximation, also known as SSQ (Sum Square of residual), is very important for determining the best local linear model.

In the global approximation theorem, all linear parameters are approximated simultaneously in a single LS optimization. The parameter vector contains all $n = M(p + 1)$ parameters of the local linear neuro-fuzzy model with M neurons and p inputs

$$\underline{w} = [w_{10} w_{11} \dots w_{1p} w_{20} w_{21} \dots w_{2p} \dots w_{M0} w_{M1} \dots w_{Mp}]^T \quad (2.29)$$

The corresponding regression matrix \underline{X} for N measured data samples becomes

$$\underline{X} = [\underline{X}_1 \underline{X}_2 \cdots \underline{X}_M] \quad (2.30)$$

with the regression submatrices

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Phi_i(u(1)) & u_1(1) \Phi_i(u(1)) & u_2(1) \Phi_i(u(1)) & \dots & u_p(1) \Phi_i(u(1)) \\ \Phi_i(u(2)) & u_1(2) \Phi_i(u(2)) & u_2(2) \Phi_i(u(2)) & \dots & u_p(2) \Phi_i(u(2)) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \Phi_i(u(N)) & u_1(N) \Phi_i(u(N)) & u_2(N) \Phi_i(u(N)) & \dots & u_p(N) \Phi_i(u(N)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.31)$$

the model output
is thus given by

$$\hat{y} = \underline{X} \cdot \underline{w} \quad (2.32)$$

In global approximation, the following loss function is minimized with respect to the parameters:

$$I = \sum_{j=1}^N e^2(j) \rightarrow \min_{\underline{w}} \quad (2.33)$$

where $e(j) = y(j) - \hat{y}(j)$ represent the model errors for the data sample $u(j), y(j)$. The globally optimal parameters can be calculated as (for $N > M(p+1)$) (see Section 3.1 Least Squares)

$$\underline{w} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T y \quad (2.34)$$

where $y = [y(1)y(2) \dots y(N)]^T$ contains the measured process outputs [Nel20, S. 407–410].

2.3.8 Normalized Mean Square Error

Normalized mean square error or NRMSE is a calculation method that examines the relationship between the simulation result and the real signal. In this way, it is distinguished which local linear model is the better choice before the quality measures and control quality are calculated. This method provides the opportunity to compare the LOLIMOT results of the loading bridge system. In other words, it allows understanding how large the deviation is when comparing the input signal that we feed into the algorithm with the result obtained as the output of the algorithm.

$$NRSME = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y(i) - \hat{y}(i))^2}{\sum_{j=1}^N (y(i) - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (2.35)$$

[HAR]

2.3.9 LOLIMOT Model Output Approximation

The equation used to represent all nonlinear systems in general

$$\hat{y} = f(\underline{\varphi}(k)) \quad (2.36)$$

where the regression vector $\underline{\varphi}(k)$ represents delayed and current process input values, delayed process or model outputs, and old approximation errors. Two different types of output data can be approximated, of which models with and without output feedback. Our system here is a model with feedback NOE (Output Error Arrangement) [Nel96] system and the other is a model with NARX (Equation Error Arrangement) [Nel96]. The following equations describe the NARX and NOE systems.

$$NOE : \underline{\varphi}(k) = [u(k-1) \cdots u(k-m) \hat{y}(k-1) \cdots \hat{y}(k-m)]^T \quad (2.37)$$

$$NARX : \underline{\varphi}(k) = [u(k-1) \cdots u(k-m) y(k-1) \cdots y(k-m)]^T \quad (2.38)$$

So far, NOE has been used in the present system. It will be explained why NOE is preferred by making a comparison with NARX. As the names of the models suggest, it is used to calculate the output values of nonlinear systems. These used values are trained in NARX in a serial-parallel configuration and the NOE model is trained in a parallel model configuration. NARX and NEO have become much more useful methods as the complex structures of nonlinear systems increase (see further [Nel20, P.845]). If the quality measures are to have the desired value, $e(k) = y(k) - \hat{y}(k)$ should be kept as small as possible. The NARX model should be used for training when the model is to be applied for one-step prediction. The NARX model exactly minimizes this one-step prediction error and is easier to train than NOE. When the intended model is a simulation, the situation is less clear. On the one hand, the NOE model is advantageous because it provides the optimal simulation error, which is precisely the goal of modeling. On the other hand, the NARX model is easier to maintain, especially when \hat{y} is linearly parameterized. Thus, both model structures can be used meaningfully. NOE better matches the modeling goal; NARX is only an approximation since it minimizes the one-step prediction error, but as compensation it offers other advantages such as simpler and faster training [Nel20, P.846].

2.3.10 Local Model Networks for Identifying Nonlinear State Space Models

In the meantime, it is explained how the state space model is prepared, which was obtained from the mathematical model that we achieved with the LOLIMOT algorithm. Important computational developments in recent years show the transition from linear system identification to non-linear system identification [SMN19b, S. 1] In

the following, the coefficient values (coefficient) of each local model (LLM) resulting from our system will later be represented as a matrix as follows. Coefficients created for a model in each iteration of the LOLIMOT algorithm are written as in the following equation. The values calculated here are x_1 (carriage position), x_3 (rope angle), x_5 (rope length) and an output signal for each value. The state space must be preserved. Of course, 4 local linear models exist for each output signal in the algorithm and separate state space values are needed for this.

$$\hat{y}(k) = \sum_{l=1}^m \left(w_{l0} + \sum_{i=1}^n \left[w_{li}^y y(k-i) + \sum_{j=1}^m w_{li}^{u_j} \cdot u_j(k-i) \right] \right) \Phi_l(u(k)) \quad (2.39)$$

Here M represents the number of local models, m the number of input signals and n the total number of data. Also w represents the constant local relative coefficient in value. Φ represents the weighting matrix that depends on the input signals. Φ weights the output signal from the models at each iteration.

$$u(k) = [u_1(k-1) u_1(k-2) \cdots u_1(k-n) u_2(k-1) \cdots u_2(k-n) \cdots \\ u_m(k-1) \cdots u_m(k-n) y(k-1) y(k-2) \cdots y(k-m)]^T$$

Three different LOLIMOT models were created for carriage position, rope angle, and rope length. The u_k input values are taken equally for each LOLIMOT model. The w values were obtained by the LOLIMOT algorithm. Given all these improved values, the state space representation model of our system is created as follows. The resulting state space model is not a minimal representation. The procedure proposed in the present work yields a minimal realization, which is given in equation (9). It is based on the analytical derivation of a state space representation in observable canonical form from the current delayed inputs and outputs and the LoLiMoT model. This initial model is a local approximation of the LoLiMoT model. In a second step, a regional approximation of the model is calculated. Therefore, the parameters obtained from the LoLiMoT model are used as starting values for an optimization procedure. To calculate the regional approximation around the given operating point, the LoLiMoT model is excited with an identification signal. Using this data, the parameters of the state space model are identified. The proposed technique is outlined below [RSH14]. Output "y" can be rewritten as;

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(-a_{n-i}(k) y(k-i) + \sum_{j=1}^m b_{n-i}^{u_j}(k) u_j(k-i) \right) + w_k^d u_d \quad (2.40)$$

$$w_k^d = \sum_{l=1}^M w_{l0} \Phi_l(u(k)) \quad (2.41)$$

here w_k^d , $b_{n-i}^{u_j}(k)$, $a_{n-i}(k)$ can be calculated as follows;

$$b_{n-i}^{u_j}(k) = \sum_{l=1}^M w_{li}^{u_j} \varphi(u_k) a_{n-i}(k) = - \sum_{l=1}^m w_{li}^y \Phi_l(u_k) \quad (2.42)$$

Here the virtual input signal u_d is represented as a fixed value, except for the previously specified values and $w_d(k)$ is its coefficient value. The state space representation prepared below is created for further use in predictive control. Since there are m inputs and one output, the observable canonical form is used. It should be noted that in Equation (2.44) the following state space realization with time-varying system parameters is used:

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+d) &= A(k)x(k) + B(k)u(k) + b_1(k)Ud \\ y_k &= C_k^T x_k \end{aligned} \quad (2.43)$$

with,
System Matrix

$$A(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & -a_0(k) \\ 1 & \ddots & & \vdots & -a_1(k-1) \\ 0 & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & -a_{n-2}(k-n+2) \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \ddots & 1 & -a_{n-1}(k-n+1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.44)$$

Input Matrix

$$b(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ w_d(k+1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.45)$$

$$B(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dots & -b_0(k) \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & -b_{n-1}(k-n+1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.46)$$

$$c(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.47)$$

The parameters of the future time points $k+1, \dots, k+n$ are needed. Since these values are unknown at time k , the following approximation is proposed: It is assumed that the system dynamics are slow compared to the sampling rate [JAK14].

2.4 Standard Control Loop

Controlling is a process in which the actual state of a system is continuously monitored and compared with the desired state through feedback. If deviations occur, they are influenced and corrected by a manipulated variable. The resulting sequence of effects takes place in a closed control loop, which is responsible for the course of a control process. As shown in Fig.2.7 the schematic representation of a standard

Figure 2.7 Schematic representation of a standard control loop.

control loop is shown, in which the controlled variable $y(t)$ is continuously measured and compared with the reference variable $w(t)$. subsequently follows the comparison element

$$e(t) = w(t) - y(t) \quad (2.48)$$

The difference determined here serves as the input variable for the controller. From this, a suitable manipulated variable $u(t)$ is calculated and transmitted to the controlled system, which can be kept constant or variable in a targeted manner via the controller. In real systems, there are almost always disturbance variables that can have undesirable effects on the control of a system behavior. In the control loop, the disturbance variable $d(t)$ acts on the controlled system. The main goal is to eliminate the steady-state control deviation

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e(t) = 0 \quad (2.49)$$

2.5 Discretization

Physical and technical processes predominantly exhibit a time-continuous system dynamics. Given physical laws describe the relationship between variables defined over continuous time, e.g., pressures $p(t)$, mass $m(t)$, forces $F(t)$, accelerations $a(t)$, or temperatures $T(t)$. Time-continuous models arise from modeling with corresponding

physical relationships. Often, the resulting model is the time-continuous, generally nonlinear state space model introduced in the previous section

$$\dot{x} = f(x(t), u(t)) \quad (2.50)$$

$$y(t) = h(x(t), u(t)) \quad (2.51)$$

which is called a continuous-discrete model. Compared to the continuous model, nothing has changed in the functions f and h . The model can still fundamentally calculate the value of the output variable for various points in time. It is therefore irrelevant whether it is a continuous or a continuous-discrete model. For system identification, however, as well as for control, this is crucial. In a continuous-discrete model, measurements of the output variable are only available at specific points in time $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Only these measured values can be used for system identification or control. Identification methods that require the continuous course of the output variable $y(t)$ can only be used if this course can be reconstructed with sufficient accuracy from the measurements at the times t_t , e.g., by interpolation.

Instead of a time-continuous dynamics of the model, a time-discrete dynamics is often intended. This is the case, for example, in linear control engineering when the input signal $u(t)$ is constant between two sampling instants. That means it is a step-shaped signal. Then the time-discrete transfer function $G(z)$ can be calculated from the continuous transfer function $G(s)$ using the exact Z-transform. However, the continuous state space model can also be converted into a time-discrete state space model using the corresponding conversion relationships [UNB09]. A time-invariant, time-discrete general state space model has the form

$$x_d(k+1) = t_d(x_d(k), u(k)) \quad (2.52)$$

$$y_d(k) = h(x_d(k), u(k)) \quad (2.53)$$

Under certain conditions, an exact conversion of the time-continuous model into a time-discrete model is possible for linear, time-invariant systems. For example, if the input signal $u(t)$ is constant between two sampling instants, i.e., it is a step-shaped signal. Then the time-discrete transfer function $G(z)$ can be calculated from the continuous transfer function $G(s)$ using the exact Z-transform. Furthermore, the continuous state space model can be determined into a time-discrete state space model using the corresponding conversion relationships [UNB09]. For nonlinear systems, such an exact discretization is generally not possible. The state variable $x(k+1)$ resulting from (Equation 4.1) by integration according to

$$x(k+1) = x(k) + \int_k^{k+1} f(x(t), u(t)) dt \quad (2.54)$$

at time $k + 1$ is therefore not identical to $x_d(k + 1)$ from (Equation 4.3). Provided that the discretized model is a good approximation for the continuous model,

$$x_d(k + 1) \approx x(k + 1) \quad (2.55)$$

should hold. This is equivalent to

$$f_d(x_d(k), u(k)) \approx x(k) + \int_k^{k+1} f(x(t), u(t)) dt \quad (2.56)$$

For example, using the trapezoidal rule as an approximation of the integral on the right-hand side, an approximate discretization can be performed. This has effects on system identification insofar as, due to the approximation, unknown system parameters of the continuous model can no longer be approximated sufficiently accurately via the approximately discretized model. If a very accurate approximation of parameters of the continuous model is necessary, it may be useful to retain the continuous system dynamics and work with a continuous-discrete model [BU16].

2.6 State Controller Using LMI

Compared to techniques that minimize a scalar function for optimization, LMI (linear matrix inequality) techniques offer more flexibility in the design of dynamic linear systems. For linear state space models, multiple objectives (performance bounds) can be described in terms of LMIs. These can serve as a basis for controller optimization via finite-dimensional convex feasibility problems. LMI formulations of various standard control problems are described in this work, including dynamic feedback stabilization [BS20, S. 1].

The system is controlled to a dynamic and time-discrete state space model, therefore the control is performed based on LMI as mentioned above. The aim is to find a memoryless controller that asymptotically stabilizes the system. Usually, approaches assume that the time interval between two signals is variable but bounded with $T_a = 0.015s$. Because of this formulation as time-varying, sampling time and the memoryless execution of the controller, these controllers can cope with both long delays and packet losses during data transmission. Since the LMI design of asymptotically stable controllers is based on the Lyapunov function, these controllers are generally sluggish because overshoot was excluded during design. In the following, advantages and disadvantages of LMI controllers are explained.

Advantages (1) LMIs are suitable as control designs for multivariable systems, (2) and they tolerate longer time delays and packet losses during data transmission. A disadvantage is (1) the sluggish controller, (2) and the design also ignores the cost function. Furthermore, (3) the solvability of the linear matrix inequalities is not guaranteed. (4) Also, it is not certain that a controller can be calculated at all [Hör15, S.49-50].

2.6.1 Linear Combination of System Matrices and Stability Analysis

Before a control unit is created for a dynamic system, it must first be determined whether the system is stable or not. In dynamic systems, stability analyses are generally attempted via energy change. If the energy in the system decreases, this means that the system is in a stable state, otherwise the system becomes unstable. For this, the Lyapunov stability method is used. Under this title, this stability method is formulated and briefly described. The system is a nonlinear dynamic system and we will try to achieve the desired carriage position, angle, and rope length values considering the system constraints.

Before the stability analysis, all local linear models are first combined using the linear convex combination method using the following equations.

The system matrices A_α are correspondingly restricted to a convex set of linear

system matrices A_i with $i = 1, \dots, M$, which exactly corresponds to the application case of an LMN in combination with LLM and a unit partitioning of the weighting function.

$$A(\alpha) = \text{Conv} \{x_j\} = \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^N A_j \cdot \rho_j, \sum_{j=1}^N \rho_j = 1, \rho_j \geq 0 \right\} \quad (2.57)$$

After the linear combination process, the stability analysis of the LMs can now proceed.

The global stability of a dynamic system can generally be calculated using Lyapunov's direct method. For this, a quadratic Lyapunov function is represented by the following equation.

$$V(x[k]) = x^T[k] \cdot P_x[k] \quad (2.58)$$

introduced with $P = P^T > 0$, $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a \times n_a}$. The system defined in equation (2.47) is asymptotically stable if the following conditions are satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} V(x[k+1]) - V(x[k]) &= x^T[k+1] \cdot P_x[k+1] - x^T[k] \cdot P_x[k] \\ &= x^T[k] \cdot A^T(\alpha) \cdot P \cdot A(\alpha) \cdot x[k] - x^T[k] \cdot P_x[k] \\ &= x^T[k] \cdot (A^T(\alpha) \cdot P \cdot A(\alpha) - P) \cdot x[k] \text{ lt } 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

The system is correspondingly quadratically (robustly) stable for all if there exists a P which can be found using a semidefinite optimizer, such that

$$A_i^T P A_i - P < 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, M \quad (2.60)$$

are satisfied Stability [Cla20, S.48].

2.6.2 State Observer Design Based on Linear Matrix Inequalities

For all state control strategies discussed so far, it is necessary that information about the actual state value is available at all times. The same applies to the system outputs that are included in the output-feedback approaches. If these two sets of vectors are not directly accessible through usable measurements, they must be reconstructed by state approximation procedures. This approximation can then be determined analogously to the feedback-control design. Details regarding implementations using linear matrix inequalities for observer design are summarized below. For linear dynamic system models in the form

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= A \cdot x(k) + B \cdot u(k) \\ y(k) &= C \cdot x(k) \end{aligned} \quad (2.61)$$

a suitable observer approach is defined by the set of the difference equations

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{x}(k+1) &= A \cdot \hat{x}(k) + B \cdot u(k) + L \cdot (y_m(k) - \hat{y}(k)) \\ \hat{y}(k) &= C \cdot \hat{x}(k)\end{aligned}\quad (2.62)$$

As in the continuous-time case, the estimated state vector is denoted by $\hat{x}(k)$, while the output estimates of the system are given by $\hat{y}(k)$ with observer gain matrix L . To guarantee asymptotic stability of the estimation error dynamics, the difference equation

$$e(k+1) = (A - LC) \cdot e(k) \quad (2.63)$$

needs to be asymptotically stable. This coincides with the asymptotic stability of a discrete-time dynamic system with transposed system matrix according to

$$e(k+1) = (A - LC)^T \cdot e(k) = (A^T - C^T L^T) \cdot e(k) \quad (2.64)$$

Hence, following the same steps as for the state feedback control design with Lyapunov function candidate

$$V(e(k)) = \frac{1}{2} e^T(k) \cdot P_o \cdot e(k) \quad (2.65)$$

Here P_o represents the energy matrix, this matrix shows how the system behaves. The P_o values should tend to decrease, if they decrease, this means the system is stable, if they tend to increase, then the system tends to be unstable.

Third, setting

$N = KQ$ with the unknown controller gain matrix

$$K = NQ^{-1} \quad (2.66)$$

leads to final linear matrix inequality

$$(A^T - C^T L^T)^T \cdot P_o \cdot (A^T - C^T L^T) - P_o < 0 \quad (2.67)$$

with

$$P_o = P_o^T > y \quad (2.68)$$

then, the duality principle of control and observer design leads to the linear matrix inequality

$$\begin{bmatrix} -Q_o & Q_o A - N_o^T C \\ A Q_o - C^T N_o & -Q_o \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (2.69)$$

with the substitutions

$$N_o = L^T \cdot Q_o, \quad L^T = N_o \cdot Q_o^{-1}, \quad \text{and} \quad N_o = L^T \cdot Q_o \quad (2.70)$$

These calculations were performed using YALMIP [LOF04] and SEDUMI [LOF04] and it was clearly seen that our system was stable as a result of these calculations [Rau17, S. 22-23].

2.6.3 State Controller Design Based on Linear Matrix Inequalities

It is possible to describe the influence of uncertainty in many practical applications by a bounded uncertainty region \mathcal{S} of a convex hull of finitely many points. It is assumed that all possible system matrices \mathbf{A} , control input matrices \mathbf{B} , and generally also the output matrices \mathbf{C} belong to a convex combination of all vertex matrices according to

$$\mathcal{S} = \{[A(\zeta), B(\zeta), C(\xi)] \mid [A(\zeta), B(\zeta), C(\zeta)] = \sum_{v=1}^{n_v} \zeta_v \cdot [A_v, B_v, C_v], \sum_{v=1}^{n_v} \zeta_v = 1; \zeta \geq 0\} \quad (2.71)$$

With the feedforward control $w(t)$ and the parameter-independent gain matrix \mathbf{K} , a robust state control law can be defined for the uncertain system Equation (2.75)

$$u(t) = w(t) - K \cdot x(t) \quad (2.72)$$

In many cases, the feedforward control is either an offline calculated sequence that guarantees perfect trajectory tracking of a nominal plant belonging to the interior of the set of systems \mathcal{S} or a stationary feedforward control

$$u(t) = K_{ff}(t) - W(t) \quad (2.73)$$

which in turn is calculated for some nominal parameter values within the uncertainty region \mathcal{S} . Substituting the control law Equation (2.76) into the ordinary differential equations corresponding to the vertex systems

$$\dot{x}(t) = A_v \cdot x(t) + B_v \cdot u(t) \quad (2.74)$$

of the uncertain plant model leads to

$$\dot{x}(t) = (A_v - B_v K) \cdot x(t) + B_v \cdot K_{ff} \cdot w(t) \quad (2.75)$$

Here, the index v denotes all vertex matrices specified in Equation (2.75) with $v = 1, \dots, n_v$

A Parameter-Independent Lyapunov Function Approach for Control Design

A sufficient condition for an asymptotically stable, parameter-independent, robust control law is that the gain matrix K satisfies the matrix inequality

$$(A_V - B_V \cdot K)^T \cdot P + P \cdot (A_V - B_V \cdot K) < 0 \quad (2.76)$$

$P = P^T > 0$, for all v .

in addition to pure Lyapunov stability as considered in [RAU17 S.13], the solution of the control design based on linear matrix inequalities can be modified in such a way that the closed-loop system has a minimum stability margin $\gamma > 0$, meaning that the real part of the eigenvalues of the closed-loop control system is guaranteed to be less than $-\gamma$ regardless of the actual parameter values. Possibilities how to add further constraints that account for certain damping ratios can, for example, be found in. The minimum stability margin can be achieved by including the term $2\gamma P$ with $\gamma > 0$ according to

$$(A_v - B_v \cdot K)^T \cdot P + P \cdot (A_v - B_v K) + 2\gamma P < 0 \quad (2.77)$$

on the left-hand side of the bilinear matrix inequality Equation (2.80). As in Section (2.1), the multiplicative couplings between K and P turn Equation (2.73) and (2.74) into bilinear matrix inequalities.

To allow for a solution of these usually non-convex problems by standard solvers like SEDUMI in combination with YALMIP, the equivalent linear matrix inequality for state-feedback control

$$A_V \cdot Q + Q \cdot A_v^T - B_v Y - Y^T B_v^T + 2\gamma Q < 0 \quad (2.78)$$

with $Q = Q^T > 0$ is used instead.

Equation (2.82) is obtained by left and right multiplying the bilinear matrix inequality Equation (2.74) by the regular matrix P^{-1} . Here, the parameter-independent matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{Y} in Equation (2.82) are related to the original unknowns by the equalities $Q = P^{-1}$ and $Y = KP^{-1}$.

if a common, parameter-independent solution \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{Y} can be found for all $v = 1, \dots, n_v$ in Equation (2.82) using numerical solution procedures (for example, SEDUMI in combination with YALMIP), the robustly stabilizing feedback gain matrix S_{FF} computed as

$$K_{ff} = \left(C_n \cdot (-A_n + B_n \cdot K)^{-1} \cdot B_n \right)^{-1} \quad (2.79)$$

with nominal matrices A_n, B_n and C_n , chosen from the domain \mathbf{D} usually does not guarantee steady-state accuracy if either additive disturbances influence the plant Equation (2.78) or if the expression

$$\left(C(\zeta) \cdot (-A(\zeta) + B(\zeta) \cdot K)^{-1} \cdot B(\zeta) \right)^{-1} \quad (2.80)$$

is not constant for variable parameters ξ . Then, the extension of the control structure by a cascaded integral feedback of the tracking error is a reasonable countermeasure. Details about such extensions can be found in [Rau17, S. 22-23].

2.6.4 Calculation of Control Performance for LMI-Based State Controller

In this work, the basis is the locally linear model-based LMI state controller, but the model results created with the LQR state controller are also needed to compare their results. For this reason, all information about the LQR state controller needed to control the loading bridge models was used. Why a cost function is needed can be better understood from the information in the corresponding source.

Vibration damping can be achieved using LQ control. For this reason, suitable state feedback is required. For the design of suitable state feedback, the quadratic quality measure see equation 2.36 is extended to

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \left(x^T(k) Q x(k) + u^T(k) R u(k) \right) dt \quad (2.81)$$

by choosing the weighting matrices Q and R as diagonal matrices with the diagonal elements

$$Q_{ii} = \mu_{x,i} \frac{1}{x_{\max,i}^2}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (2.82)$$

$$R_{j,j} = \mu_{u,j} \frac{1}{u_{\max,j}^2}, \quad j = 1, \dots, m \quad (2.83)$$

so that the largest possible value of the respective state is normalized. Thus, a weighting of the respective entered value can be carried out via the parameters $\mu_{x,i} > 0$ and $\mu_{u,j} > 0$. To assess the performance quality of LMI state controllers, one often used from LQ theory Equation (2.85) is used. The basic idea of LMI is to solve an optimal control problem online at each time k based on the measured system state $x(k)$ and system input $u(k)$. The basic optimal control problem for minimizing the quadratic cost function of the infinite horizon LMI-based control for linear time-discrete periodic systems

$$J = \sum_{i=0}^N x^T(k+1) Q x(k+1) + u^T(k+1) R u(k+1) \quad (2.84)$$

with the positive definite and symmetric weighting matrices Q and R [MRA09, S. 101].

3 Basics of the Loading Bridge

In Fig.3.1 you can see the basic view and the mechanical structure of the overhead crane system. The system consists of a rail system and a carriage. The carriage can move on the rail system. With a motor mounted on the carriage, the height of the load can be changed, so that the rope length is adjusted. On the carriage there is a winch drive with which the rope length can be varied. The transmission belt and the winch drive are driven by a current-controlled DC motor, which provides a torque proportional to the applied control voltage, so that the carriage and the winch drive can be accelerated. Using incremental encoders, the position of the carriage, the rope length and the pendulum motion of the load are measured [Gmb05].

Figure 3.1 Schematic representation of the loading bridge

The schematic representation of the loading bridge Figure (3.1) shows the overall view and next to the diagram there is a list in which each element of the loading bridge is listed. A detailed diagram is shown in the next Figure (3.2). In which very important areas and elements are shown again. So that all important formula elements can be determined for the equations of motion.

Figure 3.2 Schematic representation of the loading bridge with the three target variables

The important regions in the loading bridge are shown more clearly in Figure (3.2). When setting the input signals, the operating limits of the machine must be observed. While the rope lengths limit the movement of the load up and down, vibration occurs when the load is moved up and down and the carriage is moved at the same time. One of the fundamental goals of this study is to moderate this release and ensure that a resting position is reached. It can be seen how the ψ angle changes from -90 to $+90$. The change in carriage position consists of the total length from right to left being 1 meter, which can be defined as maximum = $+0.5$ m and minimum = -0.5 m if the center of the rail is taken as the 0 point. The rope length from top to bottom is 45 cm. If the center of the rope is taken as the center point, it can be defined as maximum = $+22.5$ cm and minimum = -22.5 cm. The aim of this study is to stay within the limits of these values. The simplest way to achieve this is to create the input signals u_1 and u_2 such that they do not exceed the maximum and minimum values, so that no unstable situation arises in the system. The values u_1 and u_2 should never be specified with the maximum and minimum values $[u_{1min} \ u_{1max}] = [-22.5N \ 22.5N]$ and $[u_{2min} \ u_{2max}] = [-3.75N \ 3.75N]$.

3.1 Mathematical Model of the System

The overhead crane represents an example of a multibody system that is typically dynamic. An important feature of this device is that it has a pendulum. For many years, this has been one of the most important battlefields in the field of engineering. The parameters required for the mathematical model can describe the entire loading bridge system as four different subsystems. These can be broken down into weight, beam, pivot point and drum. [Gmb05]. As can be seen from the cross-sectional images in Fig.3.2 below, all force values belonging to the four subsystems can be characterized mathematically.

Figure 3.3 Cross-sectional view of the subsystems according to [Gmb05]

Here, the elements in the subsystem are to be described. F_T drive force of the drum, F_A stands for the drive force of the carriage, which are the input forces of the system. The weight of the carriage is given as m_1 and the weight of the load as m_2 . The angle is ψ , which the loading bridge forms with the x-axis of the rope during vibration when carrying the load. The angle α is formed at the center of the drum with the rope. The force acting on the rope is considered as F_S . The gravitational acceleration constant is g . And finally, the forces of the rope tension exerted on the axis of rotation are F_{Ax} and F_{Ay} .

d'Alembert's principle is used for the calculation and mathematical formulation of classical dynamic systems. However, the principle of Lagrange's equations of the second kind, which is often used in mechanics, is used for modeling because of the many cross-sectional forces in this loading bridge [Gmb05].

3.2 Lagrange Equations for Dynamic Systems

With the Lagrange equations, it is possible to specify a set of exactly n equations for the n independent motion possibilities. The prerequisite for this is that the kinetic and potential energy of all bodies involved in the system is formed and expressed by the generalized coordinates and subjected to the differentiation rule. The Lagrange equation is given as follows [Gmb05]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cdot \left[\frac{\delta L}{\delta \dot{q}_j} \right] - \frac{\delta L}{\delta q_j} = Q_j \quad (j = 1, \dots, n) \quad (3.1)$$

where L is the so-called Lagrange function and is given as follows:

$$L = T - V \quad (3.2)$$

here T is the sum of the kinetic and V is the sum of the potential energies of the individual rigid bodies of the system. The forces acting on the system from outside, such as the drive forces, are given in Q_j . For the system of variable-length pendulum, the kinetic energy consists of the following three components:

Carriage :

$$T_W = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m_1 \cdot v_1^2 \quad (3.3)$$

Weight :

$$T_G = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m_2 \cdot v_2^2 \quad (3.4)$$

Drum :

$$T_T = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \theta \cdot \dot{\phi}^2 \quad (3.5)$$

Adding the three components gives the total kinetic energy T of the system:

$$T = T_w + T_G + T_T \quad (3.6)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (m_1 \cdot v_1^2 + m_2 \cdot v_2^2 + \theta \cdot \dot{\phi}^2) \quad (3.7)$$

with

$$\dot{\phi}^2 = \frac{\dot{l}^2}{R_T^2} \quad (3.8)$$

Where l is the rope length, R_T^2 is the radius of the drum. Considering the geometric relationships

$$x_1 = x_0 + l \cdot \sin(\psi) \quad (3.9)$$

$$y = -l \cdot \cos(\psi) \quad (3.10)$$

the velocities of the system result in:

$$v_1^2 = \dot{x}_0^2 \quad (3.11)$$

$$v_2^2 = \dot{x}_0^2 + \dot{l}^2 + \dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l^2 + 2 \cdot \dot{x}_0 \cdot \dot{l} \cdot \sin(\psi) + 2 \cdot \dot{x}_0 \cdot \dot{\psi} \cdot l \cdot \cos(\psi) \quad (3.12)$$

By substituting Equation (3.11) into Equation (3.7) and Equation (3.12) into Equation (3.7) the total kinetic energy T of the system results in:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \dot{x}_0^2 \cdot (m_1 + m_2) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \dot{l}^2 \cdot m_2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l^2 \cdot m_2 + \dot{x}_0^2 \cdot \dot{l} \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(\psi) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \theta \cdot \frac{\dot{l}}{R_T^2} \quad (3.13)$$

The potential energy is composed of the following components:

$$V = m_2 \cdot g \cdot y = -m_2 \cdot g \cdot l \cdot \cos(\psi) \quad (3.14)$$

The only generalizable forces of the system are the drive power for the carriage F_A , the drive force of the drum F_T and the velocity-proportional friction of the carriage F_r . This results in the following equation for the virtual processing of the system:

$$\delta W = F_A \cdot \delta r_A + F_T \cdot \delta \alpha + F_r \cdot \delta r_A \quad (3.15)$$

$$\delta r_A = \begin{bmatrix} \delta x \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \delta \alpha = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \delta \alpha \end{bmatrix} \delta F_A = \begin{bmatrix} F_A \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \delta F_T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ M_A \end{bmatrix} F_r = \begin{bmatrix} -F_r \cdot \dot{x}_0 \\ 0 \\ -F_r \cdot \dot{\alpha} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.16)$$

Now all components of the Lagrange equation are known according to Equation (3.1) [Gmb05].

3.3 Equation of Motion of the System

Since all components of the Lagrange equation are now known, the derivatives with respect to the generalized coordinates and time are formed to set up the equations of motion. After extensive calculation, the following three coupled nonlinear differential equations result:

$$\ddot{\psi} \cdot l + \ddot{x}_0 \cdot \cos(\psi) + g \cdot \sin(\psi) + 2 \cdot \dot{\psi} \cdot \dot{l} = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

$$\dot{l} \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) + x_0 \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi) - \dot{\psi} \cdot m_2 \cdot l - g \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(\psi) = F_T - F_{Tr} \cdot l \quad (3.18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x}_0 \cdot (m_1 + m_2) + \dot{l} \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi) + 2 \cdot \dot{\psi} \cdot \dot{l} \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(\psi) + \ddot{\psi} \cdot l \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(\psi) - \\ - \dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi) = F_A - F_r \cdot \dot{x}_0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Thus, the prerequisite for inducing a plant model for the variable-length pendulum has been established, and one can proceed to the state space representation [Gmb05].

3.3.1 State Space Representation of the Nonlinear Model

Since \ddot{x}_0 , $\ddot{\psi}$ and \dot{l} are required for the state space representation of the system, Equation (3.17), Equation (3.18) and Equation (3.19) must be substituted into each other and after extensive calculation the following equations are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x}_0 = \frac{(F_A - F_r \cdot \dot{x}_0) - \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_1^2} \right) + g \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \cdot \sin(\psi) \cdot \cos(\psi)}{\left(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi)^2 \right) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_1^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)} - \\ - \frac{\left(F_A - F_{Tr} \cdot \dot{l} \right) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi) + \dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_1^2} \cdot \sin(\psi)}{\left(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi)^2 \right) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_1^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)} \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

$$\ddot{\psi} = \frac{(F_T - F_{Tr} \cdot l) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi) \cdot \cos(\psi) - g \cdot \sin(\psi) \cdot \left[m_1 \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) + m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right]}{l \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi) \right]} - \frac{\dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \cdot \sin(\psi) \cdot \cos(\psi)}{l \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi) \right]} - \frac{2 \cdot \dot{\psi} \cdot \dot{l} \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi) \right]}{l \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi) \right]} - \frac{(F_{Ar}^{-F} \cdot \dot{x}_3) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) \cdot \cos(\psi)}{l \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi) \right]} \quad (3.21)$$

$$\dot{l} = \frac{(F_T - F_{Tr} \cdot l) \cdot (m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) + g \cdot m_1 \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(\psi) + \dot{\psi}^2 \cdot l \cdot m_1 \cdot m_2}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)} - \frac{(F_A - F_r \cdot \dot{x}_0) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(\psi)}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(\psi)} \quad (3.22)$$

By introducing the state vector:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \\ x_5 \\ x_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\dot{x}_1 = x_2 \quad (3.24)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = x_4 \quad (3.25)$$

$$\dot{x}_5 = x_6 \quad (3.26)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \frac{(F_A - F_r \cdot x_2) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) \cdot g \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \cdot \sin(x_3) \cdot \cos(x_3)}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)} - \frac{(F_A - F_{T_r} \cdot x_6) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(x_3) + x_4^2 \cdot x_5 \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \cdot \sin(x_3)}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)} \quad (3.27)$$

$$\dot{x}_4 = \frac{(F_T - F_{T_r} \cdot x_6) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(x_3) \cdot \cos(x_3)}{x_5 \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]} - \frac{g \cdot \sin(x_3) \cdot \left[m_1 \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) + m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right]}{x_5 \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]} - \frac{x_4^2 \cdot x_5 \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \cdot \sin(x_3) \cdot \cos(x_3)}{x_5 \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]'} \quad (3.28)$$

$$- \frac{2 \cdot x_4 \cdot x_6 \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]}{x_5 \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]'} - \frac{(F_A - F_r \cdot x_1) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) \cdot \cos(x_3)}{x_5 \cdot \left[(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)\right]'}$$

$$\dot{x}_6 = \frac{(F_T - F_{T_r} \cdot x_6) \cdot (m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) + g \cdot m_1 \cdot m_2 \cdot \cos(x_3) + x_4^2 \cdot x_5 \cdot m_1 \cdot m_2}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)} - \frac{(F_A - F_r \cdot x_2) \cdot m_2 \cdot \sin(x_3)}{(m_1 + m_2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)) \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right) - m_2^2 \cdot \sin^2(x_3)} \quad (3.29)$$

The input signals of the system are determined and displayed as shown in Figure (3.4) considering the constraints specified in the system parameters. These input signals were created using Matlab/Simulink, so that the maximum carriage movement force F_A is set to 22.5 N and the drum force of the rope lengths F_T is set to a maximum force value of 3.75 N.

Figure 3.4 Graphical representation of the inputs of the loading bridge

3.3.2 Quasi-Linearization of the Nonlinear System

Quasi-linearization around an operating point takes place when only small changes around a resting state are permitted, because then many nonlinear systems can be approximated sufficiently accurately by linear models. To linearize Equations (2.26) to (2.28), the Taylor series expansion method is applied, which is truncated after the first term. The occurring pendulum angle and angular velocity are generally small in the vicinity of their operating point, so that the following approximation:

$$\sin(\psi) = \psi, \quad \cos(\psi) = 1, \quad \dot{\psi}^2 = 0$$

can be assumed. The operating point is chosen as follows:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \\ x_5 \\ x_6 \end{bmatrix}, u_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ u_{20} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.30)$$

This gives the general form of the state space representation according to:

$$\dot{x} = A_0 \cdot x + B_0 \cdot u \quad (3.31)$$

where A_0 and B_0 are calculated as follows:

$$A_0 = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right|_{x_0, u_0} \quad \text{and} \quad B_0 = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \right|_{x_0, u_0} \quad (3.32)$$

By applying to Equations (2.26) to (2.28), the following occupancy results for the system matrix A and the control matrix B :

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{42} & a_{43} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.33)$$

Definition of the elements of the linearized system matrix A:

$$a_{22} = -\frac{F_r}{m_1}$$

$$a_{23} = \frac{g \cdot m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} - F_{T0} \cdot m_2}{m_1 \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right)}$$

$$a_{42} = -\frac{F_r}{m_d \cdot x_{50}}$$

$$a_{43} = \frac{F_{T0} \cdot m_2 - g \cdot \left[m_1 \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{z}{R_T^2}\right) + m_2 \cdot \frac{\theta}{R_T^2} \right]}{x_{50 \cdot m_1} \cdot \left(m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}\right)}$$

$$a_{66} = \frac{F_{Tr}}{m_2 + \frac{\theta}{RT^2}}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ b_{21} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ b_{41} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_{62} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.34)$$

Definition of the elements of the linearized control matrix B:

$$b_{21} = \frac{1}{m_1}$$

$$b_{41} = \frac{1}{m_1 \cdot x_{50}}$$

$$b_{62} = \frac{1}{m_2 + \frac{\theta}{R_T^2}}$$

where

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m_T \cdot R_T^2$$

and

$$F_{T_0} = -m_2 \cdot g$$

The output matrix C of the system is given by:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.35)$$

The nonlinear frictions associated with the system will be treated later. Therefore, all elements of the state space representation are defined and all prerequisites for the control loop synthesis have been created [Gmb05]. The quasi-linearized model can consequently be described by the state space representation. What a quasi-linearized form looks like has already been shown in this master's thesis. The system matrices are now entered here. The system matrix can be written as

$$A_q = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2.3636 & 0.1982 & 0.00045455 \frac{1}{x_5} & 0 & 0.2424x_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.3636 \frac{1}{x_5} & -10.0082 \frac{1}{x_5} & 0.013 \frac{1}{x_5^2} & 0 & -0.2424 \frac{x_3}{x_5} - \frac{2x_4}{x_5} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1.0505x_3 & -0.00020202 \frac{x_4}{x_5} & 0 & 4.36 \frac{1}{x_5} & -6.667 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.36)$$

the control matrix

$$B_q = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0.1818 & -0.0808x_3 \\ 0 & 0 \\ -0.1818 & 0.0808\frac{x_3}{x_5} \\ 0 & 0 \\ -0.0808x_3 & 2.2222 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.37)$$

and the output matrix

$$C_q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.38)$$

so all relevant matrices are presented. Now the quality measure with the control signals (see) Figure (3.4) is applied in a simulation and the calculated quality measures are shown in Table 3.1.

Quality Measures			
	Carriage Position	Angle	Rope Length
quasi-linear model	0.077899	37.634306	0.012548

Table 3.1 Results of the quality measures of the quasi-linear model compared to the nonlinear model

3.3.3 Linearized Model

In addition to the system parameters, it was added as A-Verladebrücke in the appendix. Further data can also be used from two sources [Gmb05], [Deh+22]. Then the following matrix values were achieved by using the principles in Section 2.3 to determine all elements of the system in the state space representation plane. Bd is the input matrix, D is the feedthrough matrix and C is the output matrix. You can see the block diagram Fig.3.3, which is created considering the classical state space equation below. Here only the system matrices are entered. The system matrix can be written as

Figure 3.5 Graphical representation of nonlinear model outputs compared to the quasilinear model

$$A_{dl} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.0147 & 0.000039608 & 0.00000036694 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.9652 & 0.0052 & 0.000061884 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.00087479 & 0.9962 & 0.0150 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.1158 & -0.5068 & 0.9940 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0.0143 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.9048 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.39)$$

the control matrix

$$B_{dl} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000020214 & 0 \\ 0.0027 & 0 \\ -0.000067292 & 0 \\ -0.0089 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.00024187 \\ 0 & -0.0317 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.40)$$

and the output matrix

$$C_l = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.41)$$

so all relevant matrices are presented. Then the state space representation is shown as a block diagram in Fig.3.5.

Figure 3.6 Block diagram of the linear state space representation of the system according to [Gmb05]

where the elements in the diagram are K controller matrix, V prefilter, D feedthrough matrix, B input signal, C output matrix and A is system matrix. If we consider the control performance of the control loop, the following values are obtained. When these values are compared with those of other prepared systems, the values obtained will be compared with the quality measures of the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm, which is the black-box model.

The following is a graphical representation of linear model outputs

In Figure (3.7) the results of the nonlinear mathematical model output and the linearized model created previously are shown. In the following sections, these values are compared with the black-box model. This allows one to understand what result was achieved and where expectations were met. As can be seen in the following graph, Figure (4.3) compares the input signal and the nonlinear output signal with the linear system. Here again, the nonlinear system is compared with the linear and quasi-linear system and the quality measures are calculated. The values compared here are carriage position (x_1), rope angle (x_3) and rope length (x_5).

An attempt is made to solve this problem with the help of a controller in Chapter (3.3.4). The results of the selected black-box model are also compared and shown in Chapter (4.2.7). Furthermore, an attempt is made to eliminate the losses and standard deviations occurring in the neuro-fuzzy controller. The most important

Figure 3.7 Graphical representation of the nonlinear mathematical model compared to the linear model

criterion here is to calculate the control performance shown in (Chapter 2.3.9) and thus provide necessary improvements.

The following graphs show the input signal, nonlinear mathematical output signals and the linear state space representation model. It can be clearly seen that these values are increased so that the system is brought to a certain level with the added controller, prefilter and observer.

Now a simulation is carried out here with the quality measure including the control signal (see) in Fig. 3.5. In Fig. 3.7 the following quality measure is calculated

Quality Measures			
	Carriage Position	Angle	Rope Length
linear model	0.000005	0.021222	1.371230

Table 3.2 Quality measures of the linear model compared to the nonlinear model

3.3.4 Luenberger Observer and State Controller

The previously determined state space representations are shown and the state controller K and the observer matrix H are calculated using the state space representation matrices. These calculated data are displayed below. Then the calculation process of the control performance is started. For the LQR control performance calculation method, the feedback matrix of the LMI observer is calculated just like for the LMI method.

Figure 3.8 Block diagram of the observer in state space representation [Gmb05]

As can be seen in Figure 3.10, nonlinear model outputs are observed using the LQR method. It is not possible to create an observer with the LMI method. Because the results with the LMI method did not achieve the expected goal. Therefore, an LMI-based controller design is used with the linear local model. But as can be seen from the graph, the results of the LQR observer will meet expectations. Further work must be done on this. For this reason, an attempt is made to achieve a better result with the LMI method by eliminating the potential nonlinear unstable states of the system with the neuro-fuzzy method. Below, the values in Table 3.3 were calculated using the SSQ method.

In the next step, an observer-based state controller is created. For this, the K controller matrices and the prefilter matrices are calculated using the equation from.

Figure 3.9 Graphical representation of LQR observer compared to the nonlinear mathematical model

Quality Measures

	Carriage Position	Angle	Rope Length
LQR based observer model	0.051880	0.171012	0.130629

Table 3.3 The quality measures of the LQR observer model compared to the nonlinear model for $x_{5AP} = 0.2m$

following LQR controller matrices K

$$K_{lqr} = \begin{bmatrix} 93.2708605067 & 40.5693246650 & -86.4261784542 \\ 1.14022411789e-13 & 6.19571062447e-14 & -5.77254714724e-14 \\ -3.89754174443 & -1.18229403745e-13 & -4.18419639663e-15 \\ 1.40502109990e-14 & -45.2898738822 & -6.66866713265 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.42)$$

where prefilter

$$V_{lqr} = \begin{bmatrix} 93.270860 & 0 \\ 0 & -45.289874 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.43)$$

Figure 3.10 Block diagram of the observer-based state controller [xxxxxx]

The block diagram shown in Fig.3.9 is extended with controller matrix K and prefilter matrices V. So that the LQR controller-based simulation is carried out with the block diagram shown in Fig.3.10.

After the simulation, the control performance equation, which can be seen in Chapter 2.3.7, is used for the calculation. The results are shown in the quality measures Table 3.3. Next, the graph shows the results of the LQR method prepared with the controllers.

Control Performance

LQR based state controller model	0.051880
----------------------------------	----------

Table 3.4 Control performance of the LQR observer-based state controller model for $x_{5AP} = 0.2m$

4 Model Building

Here, the LOLIMOT black-box model is revealed with the help of all data needed for our LOLIMOT loading bridge model. The aim is to achieve the result at each step by applying all the algorithm steps, which were explained in Chapter 2, one after another to our own system. The system is based on two input signals and three output signals.

4.1 Tasks in Model Building

Because nonlinear processes are exceptional as they do not share many features, modeling and identifying them is a challenging task. A primary goal for any modeling and identification scheme for nonlinear systems is universality. That is, the ability to characterize a broad class of structurally varying systems. Figure 1.2 shows the task of system identification. For simpler processing, it is assumed that the process has only one output. An extension to the case of multiple outputs is also straightforward. A model should represent the behavior of a process as accurately as possible. Model quality is characteristically measured as a function of the error between the (disturbed) process output and the model output. This error is used to adjust the parameters of the model. [Nel01, S. 6] A classic block diagram for system identification can be seen in Fig.2.3. The goal is to create a neuro-fuzzy model that consists of a combination of local linear models. So that the results of the algorithm used turn out well, an attempt is made to achieve the result by carrying out all the steps one after another, which were explained in the previous chapter 4 under the title Model Building.

4.1.1 Model Inputs of the Black-Box Model

Step 1 is typically realized in a trial-and-error approach using prior knowledge. The influence of different variables is usually clear in mechanical processes. The relevant model inputs can be selected based on existing insights into the physics of the process. Basically, the following four different strategies can be distinguished: (1) Use all inputs, (2) try all input combinations, (3) unsupervised input selection, and (4) supervised input selection [Nel20, S.9]. In this case, the last category, to which LOLIMOT belongs, is used. Only the last category is briefly described. Through supervised input selection, the inputs are selected with regard to the highest possible model accuracy.

Figure 4.1 Graphical representation of the input and output signals of a nonlinear model

4.1.2 Excitation Signals of the LOLIMOT Model

Before moving to step 2, an understanding of the process and the purpose of the model must exist. For black-box modeling, measurements are the most essential source of information. Only if prior knowledge is explicitly included can models describe process behavior that is not represented in the dataset. Therefore, this step limits the achievable model quality and is more important than subsequent steps. This step probably requires the most engineering skills.

If the process under consideration cannot be actively excited, the training dataset should still be designed by selecting the most representative dataset possible from the collected measurements. This requires knowledge of what the explicit design of the excitation signal looks like.

Storing information about the operating conditions covered by the training dataset (see Fig.4.2) is important to be able to assess the reliability of model predictions. This allows extrapolation to possibly be avoided or limited [Nel20, S.11]. Using the

Figure 4.2 Graphical representation of the training and validation data of the neuro-fuzzy algorithm

input and output signals of the system to obtain a highly accurate training dataset would be the most accurate procedure. The training and validation data obtained from the input and output signals, which are exemplarily shown in Figure 4.2, can be used. The most important thing is the process of obtaining other input signals that are obtained with a time-shifted delay of LOLIMOT input signals. This topic was examined in detail under the title Section (3.3.4). The signals that are used must be within the limits of the system. An example of this is the result of the algorithm as a result of the input signal shown in Figure. 4.2 below.

4.1.3 Choice of Model Architecture

Step 3 is probably the most subjectively influenced decision. Which criteria are important for selecting a suitable model architecture is shown in the following, albeit incomplete, list.

These are the following types of problems: classification, approximation of static systems or identification of dynamic systems.

The problem dimension is formed by the number of relevant inputs (and outputs), which shows the class of the corresponding model architectures.

The available amount and quality of the data must be considered. If the data is very sparse and noisy, a global approach might be more successful than a local approach, as they have a higher tendency to average out disturbances.

Next, the constraints of development, training, and evaluation time. The development time depends heavily on the degree of automation and the training time of an identification technique. The degree of automation determines how much user interaction is required. This is often related to the interpretability and the number of tuning parameters.

Memory restrictions should be considered. In areas with high volumes, such as the automotive industry, memory restrictions are still an important issue. In the future, however, these restrictions will become less important, as storage costs are falling even faster than computing costs.

Offline or online learning. While all architectures are suitable for offline training, online learning in a reliable manner is a question for further research. From today's perspective, only local modeling approaches seem suitable for this task.

Furthermore, the availability of tools and customer acceptance are important. Since the complexity of software grows exponentially over time just as the performance increase of hardware does, tools are becoming increasingly important to keep software manageable and development times short. An inherent understanding of the operation of the system is a key point in the acceptance of a new modeling and identification approach. This includes that the implemented models should be interpretable. Purely black-box solutions alone are usually not convincing [Nel20, S.12].

4.1.4 Dynamic Orders of the LOLIMOT Model

Step 5 is typically performed through a combination of trial, prior knowledge, and error. With the external-dynamics approach, choosing a higher dynamic order of the model increases the dimensionality of the problem and thus its complexity. Compared to linear system identification, the user may often be forced to accept significant unmodeled dynamics when dealing with nonlinear systems by choosing too low a model order. The reason for this is a compromise between the errors introduced by neglected dynamics and the static approximation error. Because the overall complexity of the model is limited by the bias/variance dilemma, a high dynamic order of the model (increasing its dimensionality) may have to be paid for by a loss of static approximation accuracy. Nelles states that low-order models are often sufficient in his experience, since the model error is dominated by the approximation error caused by an inaccurate description of the process nonlinearity [Nel20, S.13]. In this work, different input signals were used and new experiments were conducted depending on the result. For example, sometimes the number of inputs was used as $[u_1 \ u_1 - 1 \ u_2 \ u_2 - 1 \ y - 1 \ y - 2 \ y]$. Thus, the LOLIMOT algorithm was continued until the best result was achieved. The result was then compared with the validation signals in Fig. 4.2.

$$u_{oli} = [u_1 \cdots (u_1 - 1) \quad u_2 \cdots (u_2 - 1) \quad y - 1 \cdots y - 2] \quad (4.1)$$

4.1.5 Model Structure and Complexity

Step 6 is even more difficult than parameter optimization. It can be automated if structure optimization techniques such as Orthogonal Least Squares (OLS) for linearly parameterized models or Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) for nonlinearly parameterized models are applied. Alternative to these general approaches are module-specific growth and/or pruning algorithms, such as LOLIMOT for local linear neuro-fuzzy models, ASMOD for additive singleton neuro-fuzzy systems, or the large variety of algorithms available for multi-layer perceptron networks. Especially in industry, many problems are still solved with non-automated trial-and-error approaches, although a considerable number of sophisticated algorithms have been developed for these tasks. The main reasons for the following shortcomings of automatic algorithms are long training times

- , a large number of tuning parameters to be determined
- , no or limited suitability for dynamic models
- , and limited software support in the form of toolboxes.

With the Local Linear Model Tree (LOLIMOT) algorithm presented in Section (2.3.2), these handicaps can be significantly reduced or even overcome. Nevertheless, many obstacles of complexity and structure optimization still need to be overcome for research. Step 6 seems to be the most promising for an advantageous integration

of different information sources such as measurement data, qualitative knowledge equations from first principles. Step 7 is predominantly driven by measurement data, since efficient and accurate optimization techniques are available, while steps 1 to 3 are mainly based on prior knowledge [Nel20, S.13].

4.1.6 Optimization of Model Parameters

Step 7 is the easiest to automate. It is usually solved by applying linear and non-linear optimization techniques. While linear optimization techniques work fully automatically, nonlinear optimization typically requires some user interaction. Depending on the chosen method, initial estimates of the parameters and optimization procedure-specific parameters must be determined by the user. Nevertheless, parameter optimization techniques are in a mature state. They are easy to use and many toolboxes are available. Current research focuses on problems with constraints, with a large number of parameters, with multiple objectives, or with a global search objective [Nel20, S.13].

4.1.7 Model Validation

Step 7 checks whether all previous steps were carried out successfully or not. The criteria used to make this decision are particularly problem-dependent. In many cases, the model serves rather as a basis for further steps, such as the design of a controller or a fault detection system, and is not the final goal. The state space representation system and the control gain are calculated in Chapter 5. Subsequently, the correct criteria may be the performance of the control system or the sensitivity of fault detection. So that the calculated control error can be compared with the LQ control system. Before the model is used as a basis for further steps, the model quality is directly examined to decouple modeling and subsequent design as much as possible.

If the performance achieved with the training data is acceptable, it is necessary to test the model with fresh validation data. The more complex the model and the smaller the noisy training dataset, the more the need for this separate test dataset increases. The validation data should excite the process and the model in particular under those operating conditions that are considered important for the later use of the model. The test data should excite at frequencies around the expected bandwidth of the closed control loop. The steady-state properties of a model used for fault detection, on the other hand, may be more relevant. Often enough prior knowledge about the process is available to recognize unrealistic model responses and revise the model. If one only examines the model based on training and validation data, many details can be overlooked. [Nel20, S. 15]. The image below shows an example of a typical output of the LOLIMOT algorithm, where the output signals of the process are compared and the error value is minimized. To represent the process behavior, a

Figure 4.3 Representation of the block diagram of system identification according to [Nel20, S. 14]

model is fitted. Process and model are fed with the same inputs $u = [u_1 \ u_2 \ \dots \ u_p]$, and their outputs y and \hat{y} are compared and result in the error signal e , which can be used to adjust the model. Note that the process output is usually disturbed by noise G .

After many experiments with the LOLIMOT algorithm, the results of 4 iterations yielded an almost perfect result. The following (see Fig.4.4) contains the comparison of the results of the different experiments conducted previously. As can be seen, the error rate decreases as the number of iterations increases, and the LOLIMOT signal result approaches the target value.

In (see Fig.4.5) the best model of the LOLIMOT algorithm is shown in comparison to the nonlinear model. By looking, one can see very clearly that the carriage position is very close to the target value, the rope angle has a large difference, and finally the rope length meets expectations with small deviations.

Figure 4.4 Results of four iterations of the LOLIMOT algorithm for carriage position, rope angle and rope length

Model Results of RMSE and Quality Measures

The best method to compare several models with each other is the SSQ method or the known quality measure. For this reason, we need to calculate the quality measures to better analyze the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm; the necessary formula was given in Section (2.3.7). We calculated the same formulas in the quasi-linear models, the linear models and the results in see Section (3.3.2) and Section (3.3.3). Now we have calculated the same process based on the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm in the following table. And these values are also shown in (see Fig.4.5). Furthermore, the results of the quasi-linear and linear models are compared with the LOLIMOT results in another diagram. The most important thing here is that the LOLIMOT results, which we obtained without physical data or data calculation procedures, have really yielded values that far exceed our expectations.

The SSQ and NRMSE values shown in the table above are visualized again in the graph below. As can be seen from the graph, the SSQ value overlaps as the number of iterations increases.

Figure 4.5 Graphical representation of the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm for carriage position, rope angle and rope length in comparison to the nonlinear model

	Quality Measures				NRMSE			
	1.LLM	2.LLM	3.LLM	4.LLM	1.LLM	2.LLM	3.LLM	4.LLM
x_1 Carriage Position	133.82	13.43	10.27	1.004	0.3728	0.0843	0.0450	0.02017
x_3 Rope Angle	120.193	114.560	110.673	124.568	0.0733	0.0687	0.0693	0.0715
x_5 Rope Length	3.89357	0.418302	0.484403	0.264173	0.0652	0.0507	0.0499	0.0409

Table 4.1 Quality Measures and NRMSE results of the local linear model

In Figure 4.6, one thing to note is that the LOLIMOT model cannot sometimes continue with a decreasing error rate in each iteration if the input signals are not well chosen. Input signal values outside the capabilities of the plant can sometimes cause unavoidable nonlinear responses. For example, while the error rate tends to decrease in the rope angle model in the 3rd iteration, the rate tends to increase again in the 4th iteration. Since the input signal is created in Simulink/Matlab, it makes sense to create it considering trial-and-error methods and the operating limits of the plants.

Figure 4.6 NRMSE and the quality measures of four local linear models

Here, all quality measure results of the models are presented. see Figure (4.7) already shows that the large quality measure values belong to the LOLIMOT algorithm results. But the local model network does not need any additional physical data at all. If the training procedure is improved, the results will always improve.

Figure 4.7 Comparison of the quality measure results of all models

4.2 State Space Representation of the Best Local Model Network

To prepare the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm by using a state space representation here, using the equations in Section (2.3) from Equation (2.48) to (2.51) the following system, input, output and feedthrough matrices are prepared for each output signal x_1 , x_3 and for x_5 . Later, these matrices are combined with the linear combination method, but this linear combination process is simulated dynamically. If the quality measures shown in Fig.4.5, our best model, are examined, it can be evaluated with 4. LLMs for x_1 , 4. LLMs for x_3 and 4. LLMs for x_5 .

The following matrices form the local model. A1 to A4 represent system matrices. B1 to B4 represent input matrices. C1 to C4 represent output matrices and D1 to D4 represent feedthrough matrices, so that all matrices from LLM_1 to LLM_4 can be formed

Local Linear Model State Space Representation (LOLIMOTSS) of the Carriage Position

System matrices of the carriage position

$$A1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00003 & -0.0000009 & 1.963850 & -0.963827 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

$$A2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00003 & 0.000000003 & 1.967472 & -0.967472 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

$$A3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00003 & 0.000000003 & 1.967596 & -0.967596 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

$$A4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000037 & 0.0000005 & 1.949979 & -0.949991 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.5)$$

Input matrices of the carriage position

$$B1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0000009 & -0.0000009 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

$$B2 = \begin{bmatrix} 9.751531797782156e - 07 & -9.46111734748424e - 07 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.7)$$

$$B3 = \begin{bmatrix} 9.751531797782156e - 07 & -9.46111734748424e - 07 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.8)$$

$$B4 = \begin{bmatrix} 9.751531797782156e - 07 & -9.46111734748424e - 07 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9)$$

Output matrices and feedthrough matrices of the carriage position

$$C1 \dots C4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad D1 \dots D4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10)$$

Local Linear Model State Space Representation (LOLIMOTSS) of the Rope Angle

System matrices of the rope angle

$$A1 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.132018 & -3.731070 & 2.035519 & -0.436984 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.11)$$

$$A2 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.091880 & -3.703983 & 2.101816 & -0.492133 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.12)$$

$$A3 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.082567 & -3.662289 & 2.038038 & -0.460378 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.13)$$

$$A4 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.082567 & -3.662289 & 2.038038 & -0.460378 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.14)$$

Input matrices of the rope angle

$$B1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.469942296932177 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.15)$$

$$B2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.001825073233831 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.16)$$

$$B3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.977772229162496 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.17)$$

$$B4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.001664630386942 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.18)$$

Output matrices C and feedthrough matrices D of the rope angle

$$C1 \dots C4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad D1 \dots D4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.19)$$

Local Linear Model State Space Representation (LOLIMOTSS) of the Rope Length

System matrices of the rope length (x_5)

$$A1 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.132018 & -3.731070 & 2.035519 & -0.436984 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.20)$$

$$A2 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.091880 & -3.703983 & 2.101816 & -0.49213 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.21)$$

$$A3 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.082567 & -3.662289 & 2.038038 & -0.460378 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.22)$$

$$A4 = \begin{bmatrix} 3.082567 & -3.662289 & 2.038038 & -0.460378 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.23)$$

Input matrices of the rope length

$$B1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000002 & -0.000002 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.24)$$

$$B2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0000002 & 0.0000000002 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.25)$$

$$B3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0000003 & 0.0000000002 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.26)$$

$$B4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0000003 & 0.0000000006 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.27)$$

Output matrices C and feedthrough matrices D of the rope length

$$C1...4 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad D1 \dots D4 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.28)$$

All matrices obtained in the next chapter are combined with the linear combination method. An attempt is made to control the system with LMI-based observers and controllers, which will be created later.

where, A_{lm} Local models linearly combined system matrix, B_{lm} control matrix, C_{lm} output matrix, D_{lm} feedthrough matrix and linear combination of the state space representation. In linear combination of the state space representation, weighting matrix multiplication with the n-th iteration of LLMs state space representation matrices occurs.

Figure 4.8 Block diagram of the state space representation of the LOLIMOT model

4.3 Linear Combination of the Local Models

First, the matrices obtained from the LOLIMOT algorithm are combined using the weighting function. Particular focus here is on the simulation of the values obtained by multiplying with the weighting function to obtain the state space result of the system.

During the system identification process carried out with the Lolimot algorithm, the best model selection was made using the SSQ value method. These values are 1.0004 for carriage position, 124.64 for rope angle and 0.2641 for rope length see Table 4.1, where the fourth local linear model was chosen for each desired value of the loading bridge. The following is an example calculation for 4 iterations using equation 2.21 of the matrices obtained from the coefficients of the input signals. The coefficients were calculated from the results of the algorithm using the linear combination method. This example calculation will show how the local linear model dynamically switches the system matrices and input matrices with the sampling time T_a in each k -iteration using the function. In (see Chapter 2.6.1) an equation (see 2.61) the following Φ_i matrix and linear combination A and B matrices were calculated. The sum of the Φ_i matrix should be equal to 1 in each iteration.

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} 0.000616 & 0.499938 & 0.499938 & 0.000616 \\ 0.000616 & 0.499938 & 0.499938 & 0.000616 \\ 0.000616 & 0.499938 & 0.499938 & 0.000616 \\ 0.000616 & 0.499938 & 0.499938 & 0.000616 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.29)$$

when equation 2.21 is performed, the linear combination of system matrix and input matrix is calculated as follows.

$$A_{LinKom} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.831 & -0.83000 & -0.00476 & 0.003731 \\ 0.999 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.99 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.99 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.30)$$

$$B_{LinKom} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.42499 & -2.01403 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.31)$$

$$C_{LinKom} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.469942 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.32)$$

5 Design of Observer-Based State Control

In the meantime, the values after the stability analysis are presented using the LMI method explained in Chapter 2.6. Then, the calculations required for the observer design of the observer matrix and the K calculation for the controller matrix are performed. These results are shown here as a graph. The system is a MIMO system and the target values are obtained as outputs of x_1 , x_3 and x_5 .

LMI-based observer matrices of each local model network are calculated from the local linear model using the YALMIP and SEDUMI toolbox.

5.1 LMI-based Observer using LOLIMOTSS

Observer is an LMI-based neuro-fuzzy state space observer. The advantage of this system is that it is dynamic and weights the state space representation matrices with the weighting function in each iteration. The system consists of the combination of the weighting function that the neural system uses to eliminate the nonlinearity of the state space representation matrices of the local linear models. The advantages of the neuro-fuzzy system are fully exploited. The observer systematically checks the nonlinear model with each iteration.

Observer H matrix,

$$Hlm_{x_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.90179641496799 & 0.00886587182493130 & 1.34208298073030e-17 \\ 60.0597603705563 & 0.316565536971815 & 8.32904749303745e-16 \\ 0.126649800848951 & 1.71205956150039 & 9.80565118459372e-19 \\ 11.7316211211442 & 51.6403226372451 & 1.46544578018503e-17 \\ -1.19508030923747e-15 & 6.43939433256034e-15 & 0.0966755567123049 \\ -5.18145000258563e-16 & 5.95013344803575e-14 & 0.236424922249399 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

$$Hlm_{x_3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.90179641496799 & 0.00886587182493130 & 1.34208298073030e-17 \\ 60.0597603705563 & 0.316565536971815 & 8.32904749303745e-16 \\ 0.126649800848951 & 1.71205956150039 & 9.80565118459372e-19 \\ 11.7316211211442 & 51.6403226372451 & 1.46544578018503e-17 \\ -1.19508030923747e-15 & 6.43939433256034e-15 & 0.0966755567123049 \\ -5.18145000258563e-16 & 5.95013344803575e-14 & 0.236424922249399 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.2)$$

$$Hlm_{x_5} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.90179641496799 & 0.00886587182493130 & 1.34208298073030e-17 \\ 60.0597603705563 & 0.316565536971815 & 8.32904749303745e-16 \\ 0.126649800848951 & 1.71205956150039 & 9.80565118459372e-19 \\ 11.7316211211442 & 51.6403226372451 & 1.46544578018503e-17 \\ -1.19508030923747e-15 & 6.43939433256034e-15 & 0.0966755567123049 \\ -5.18145000258563e-16 & 5.95013344803575e-14 & 0.236424922249399 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

The block diagram in Figure (5.1) shows the state space representation observer, which was created with the values obtained from the LOLIMOT algorithm. Here,

5.2 LMI-based State Controller using LOLIMOT State Space Representation

Here, an observer is first created with the matrices obtained as a result of the LOLIMOT algorithm. Then a state controller is created from this observer. The YALMIP and SEDUMI program is used to create K_{lm} . As can be seen in the block diagram below, the system can be controlled by the K_{lm} matrix.

$$Klm_{x_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1929027.272 & -266580.299444 & -8.311957 \\ 3.423007 & 1.709339 & 6.050887 \\ -252030.825 & -262442.907 & 19.837476 \\ 11.711488 & -20.99716 & -8.838173 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.4)$$

$$Klm_{x_3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1929027.272 & -266580.299 & -8.311 \\ 3.423 & 1.709 & 6.050 \\ -252030.825 & -262442.907 & 19.837 \\ 11.711 & -20.997 & -8.838 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.5)$$

$$Klm_{x_5} = \begin{bmatrix} 1929027.272 & -266580.299 & -8.31195 \\ 3.423 & 1.709 & 6.050 \\ -252030.825 & -262442.907 & 19.837 \\ 11.711 & -20.997 & -8.838 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.6)$$

In Figure 5.2, which was created as a continuation of Figure 5.1, our block diagram is supplemented with the control unit $Klmi$ calculated using the LMI method and given its final form. The results of the prepared controllers are shown in the following figure.

Figure 5.2 Block diagram of the observer-based state controller of the LOLIMOT model

Figure 5.3 Graphical representation of the nonlinear model compared to all models as well as the local linear model (LOLIMOT) outputs

As you can see in Figure 5.3, we tried to compare the LQR controller, the LMI controller, the nonlinear controller and the observer together with the nonlinear model. As can be seen, although the LQR controller provides better results, the other values are far from the desired values. Furthermore, the LMI controllers provide a value that is above expectations.

5.3 Model Simulation and Analysis of the Results

Here, the results of the LOLIMOT algorithm, i.e., the results of the created dynamic control unit, are shown. After the results of the system achieved with the LOLIMOT algorithm are explained under the title "Simulation Results", the different results are compared using some different parameters. Then the best result is commented on and one has the opportunity to compare the obtained data with observer and controls. Since our system is a black-box system, no physical data or losses due to friction need to be considered. The most important criterion, however, is the global loss and the standard deviation. Of course, there is the possibility to compare the control performance values.

Figure 5.4 Graphical representation of the nonlinear model compared to all models as well as the local linear model (LOLIMOT) outputs

As seen in Figure 5.4, the nonlinear model output and the linear model output

were compared with each other. As can be seen in the graphical representation, the results of the linear local model are very close to the target value. However, the same does not apply to the state space representation (LOLIMOTSS). Further studies are required on this topic, in particular NEO and NARX methods can be investigated more precisely and applied to the LOLIMOTSS model.

6 Conclusion

In this study, a black-box model of the overhead crane dynamic system was developed using the Local Linear Model (neuro-fuzzy model) algorithm. An attempt was made to control this black-box model with LMI-based observer-supported controllers. Using the values from the LOLIMOT algorithm, an effort was made to generate the desired output signals. The existing LOLIMOT algorithm was specifically adapted for this research project.

Before switching to the black-box model, observers were created based on both LQR and LMI methods. While the LQR observer worked correctly at every operating point, accurate results with the LMI method could only be achieved at a single operating point. This shows that the LMI method is not a technique that always delivers results comparable to LQR. Due to insufficient real data, the input and output signals required for the LOLIMOT algorithm were obtained by simulating the nonlinear model in MATLAB/Simulink. By using these simulated data as input for the LOLIMOT algorithm, the desired results were achieved without using any physical real-world data. It is important to note that the operating limits of the system must be respected. In particular, the maximum and minimum values of the input signals u_1 and u_2 must be observed. Additionally, the operating point values of the system should also be taken into account.

The calculation of performance measures and control quality — the main focus of this master thesis — was successfully carried out despite some difficulties. Although the LMI-based control design was very challenging, a functional controller was eventually developed as required. The most difficult task was selecting the right number of input signals for the LOLIMOT algorithm, because the algorithm can perform poorly if the number of inputs is either too large or too small.

The LOLIMOT algorithm, which was the main objective of this study, was successfully implemented to create a local model network. Although the complexity of the algorithm made this study very difficult and required careful consideration of many factors, we were able to successfully obtain the output signals. It is important to calculate performance measures and control quality. This was successfully achieved. Although state-space representations of local linear models could be created as observers and controllers using the Lyapunov stability method and the convex combination method, the desired result could not be fully achieved. The main reason for this was the proper selection of dynamic orders. This was attempted using the trial-and-error method. Obviously, the algorithm delivered good results, but the desired outcome could not be reached in the state-space representation model. The number of inputs to the algorithm should be chosen to match the number of trajectories of the real system. States that cause unnecessary burden on the desired output signal should be eliminated. For the local linear model, six trajectories were selected, and an LMI-based controller was designed accordingly.

The majority of the objectives were fulfilled. That is, all necessary steps of the

black-box model were completed and the desired result was achieved. In addition, the performance measures were calculated. For this purpose, the control quality for LQR was computed; however, the same level of performance could not be reached with the observer-based LMI state feedback controller. The main reason was that the input data for the LOLIMOT neuro-fuzzy system were virtual, and these input signals did not deliver the same results as expected in the state-space model. Although the algorithm delivers good results, studies should be conducted to make it faster. Furthermore, better results can be achieved by further researching the topic of parameter optimization and making the system parameters more effective. The neuro-fuzzy algorithm can, as in many AI, ML, and deep learning processes, help solve promising nonlinear systems — especially problems that exceed the current technological and physical limits of humanity. It can enable us to obtain control signals at the desired levels, particularly by eliminating highly scaled data and storage requirements in brain research, which can ensure the automation and optimal operation of machines.

Bibliography

- [Ada14] Jürgen Adamy. *Nichtlineare Systeme und Regelungen*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014. ISBN: 978-3-642-45012-9. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-45013-6.
- [BS20] John Baillieul and Tariq Samad. *Encyclopedia of Systems and Control*. London: Springer London, 2020. ISBN: 978-1-4471-5102-9. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4471-5102-9.
- [Bau03] Marcus Baur. ‘Modellierung und Regelung nichtlinearer dynamischer Mehrgrößensysteme auf der Basis von fuzzy-verknüpfen lokalen linearen Modellen’. In: *Dissertation* (2003).
- [CSL20] Jie Chen, JunWei Su, and JingYin Li. ‘Self-Coupling Black Box Model of a Dynamic System Based on ANN and Its Application’. In: *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2020 (2020), pp. 1–12. ISSN: 1024-123X. DOI: 10.1155/2020/5724831.
- [Cla20] Roland Clauß. *Funktions- und Reglersynthese auf der Basis lokaler Modellnetze*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2020. ISBN: 978-3-658-31983-0. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-31984-7.
- [Deh+22] Robert Dehnert et al. ‘Robust Feedback Control for Discrete-Time Systems Based on Iterative LMIs with Polytopic Uncertainty Representations Subject to Stochastic Noise’. In: *Frontiers in Control Engineering* 2 (2022). DOI: 10.3389/fcteg.2021.786152.
- [Gmb05] Amir GmbH. ‘Modellbildung des Systems Verladebrücke’. In: *Technical Report* (2005).
- [Har14] Benjamin Hartmann. ‘Lokale Modellnetze zur Identifikation und Versuchsplanung nichtlinearer Systeme’. PhD thesis. Universität Siegen, 2014.
- [Hör15] Wolfgang Alois Hörtnagel. ‘Optimale stochastische Regelung eines vernetzten Systems’. Master’s thesis. Technische Universität München, 2015.
- [Kus18] Dmytro Kushnir. ‘Identification of Dynamical System’s Parameters using Neural Networks’. In: *Master’s thesis* (2018).
- [Lun14] Jan Lunze. *Regelungstechnik 1: Systemtheoretische Grundlagen, Analyse und Entwurf einschleifiger Regelungen*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014. ISBN: 978-3-642-53908-4. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-53909-1.

-
- [MRA09] Lalo Magni, Davide Martino Raimondo, and Frank Allgöwer, eds. *Nonlinear Model Predictive Control: Towards New Challenging Applications*. Vol. 384. Lecture Notes in Control and Information Sciences. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2009. ISBN: 978-3-642-01093-4. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-01094-1.
- [Nel96] Oliver Nelles. ‘LOLIMOT - Lokale lineare Modelle zur Identifikation nichtlinearer dynamischer Systeme’. In: *at - Automatisierungstechnik* 44.4 (1996), pp. 163–172.
- [Nel01] Oliver Nelles. *Nonlinear System Identification: From Classical Approaches to Neural Networks and Fuzzy Models*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2001. ISBN: 978-3-662-04323-3.
- [Nel20] Oliver Nelles. *Nonlinear System Identification: From Classical Approaches to Neural Networks, Fuzzy Models, and Gaussian Processes*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020. ISBN: 978-3-030-47438-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-47439-3.
- [Rau17] Andreas Rauh. *Sensitivity Methods for Analysis and Design of Dynamic Systems with Applications in Control Engineering*. Vol. 6. Modellbildung und Regelung mechatronischer Systeme. Aachen: Shaker Verlag, 2017. ISBN: 978-3844054987.
- [RSH14] Jakob Rehrl, Daniel Schwingshackl, and Martin Horn. ‘A Modeling Approach for HVAC Systems Based on the LoLiMoT Algorithm’. In: *Proceedings of the 19th IFAC World Congress*. Cape Town, South Africa, 2014, pp. 24–29.
- [SMN19a] Max Schüssler, Tobias Münker, and Oliver Nelles. ‘Local Model Networks for the Identification of Nonlinear State Space Models’. In: *2019 IEEE 58th Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*. Nice, France: IEEE, 2019, pp. 1234–1240. DOI: 10.1109/CDC40024.2019.9029456.
- [SMN19b] Max Schüssler, Tobias Münker, and Oliver Nelles. ‘Local Model Networks for the Identification of Nonlinear State Space Models’. In: *2019 IEEE 58th Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*. Nice, France: IEEE, 2019, pp. 1234–1240. DOI: 10.1109/CDC40024.2019.9029456.
- [Stu99] Michael Sturm. ‘Neuronale Netze zur Modellbildung in der Regelungstechnik’. In: *Technische Universität München, Institut für Informatik* (1999).
- [Unb02] Rolf Unbehauen. *Systemtheorie 1: Allgemeine Grundlagen, Signale und lineare Systeme im Zeit- und Frequenzbereich*. 8th ed. München: Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag, 2002. ISBN: 978-3486259933.
-

A Definition of System Parameters

The following are the system parameters of the variable-length pendulum.
For the carriage:

Description	Constant	Value	Unit
Mass	m_1	5.5	kg
Friction constant	F_{rw}	13	kg/s
Maximum actuating force	$K_{out}W$	22.5	N
Sliding friction constant	$D_{const}w$	6.7	N
Static friction constant	$D_{haft}w$	0.5	N
Velocity interval	v_1	0.015	m/s

Table A.1 System parameters for the carriage

For the drum for changing the rope length: For the weight:

Description	Constant	Value	Unit
Mass	m_1	5.5	kg
Radius	$K_{out}W$	22.5	N
Friction constant	F_{rw}	13	kg/s
Maximum actuating force	$D_{const}w$	6.7	N
Sliding friction constant	$D_{haft}w$	0.5	N

Table A.2 System parameters for the drum

Description	Constant	Value	Unit
Mass	m_2	0.2	kg

Table A.3 System parameters for the weight

A.0.1 LOLIMOT Pseudocode Algorithm

Algorithm 2 LOLIMOT Algorithm [NB14b]

```

procedure CRANE LOCAL LINEAR MODEL IMPLEMENTATION
  Initializations
   $xc_1 = ((\min(X) + \max(X))/2)$ 
   $dx_1 = (\max(X) - \min(X))$ 
   $\sigma_1 = (1/3)$ 
   $\Phi_1 \leftarrow$  Calculate Validity Function ( $xc_1, \sigma_1, dx_1$ )
   $w_1 \leftarrow$  weighted least squared error ( $xc_1, X, y$ )
   $\hat{y}_{LLM_1} \leftarrow X \times w, \hat{y} \leftarrow \hat{y}_{LLM_1} \times \Phi_1, e \leftarrow J(y - \hat{y})$ 
   $e_{Lokal_{LLM_1}} \leftarrow \Phi_1 \times e, e_{Lokal} \leftarrow e_{Lokal_{LLM_1}}$ 
  for  $i = 1 \rightarrow LLM_{max}$  do
    ( $Neuron_{new}, Neuron_{del}$ )  $\leftarrow$  ( $Neuron_{old}, Neuron_{local}$ )
    for  $l = 1 \rightarrow InputDimension$  do
       $Splittingregion \leftarrow Findmin - maxbound(Neuron_{del})$ 
      ( $c_{new}, \sigma_{new}$ )  $\leftarrow$  CreatenewNeuron( $Splittingregion$ )
      Updated Model  $\leftarrow$  Insert into Model( $c_{new}, c_{new}, Split Dimension$ )
      for  $k = 1 \rightarrow i + 1$  do
         $\Phi_k \leftarrow Calculate(c_k, \sigma_k, X)$ 
         $w_1 \leftarrow$  weighted least squared error ( $\phi_k, X, y$ )
         $\hat{y}_{LLM_1} \leftarrow X \times w$ 
      end
       $\hat{y} \leftarrow \hat{y}_{LLM_1} \times \Phi_1, e \leftarrow J(y - \hat{y})$ 
       $e \leftarrow$  Select the minimum cost Neuron( $e_l$ )
    end
    if  $e_l < Target Accuracy$  Or Neuron Number == Present Model Complexity then
      break
      for  $k = 1 \rightarrow i + 1$  do
         $e_{Lokal_{LLM_k}} \leftarrow \Phi_k \times e$ 
      end
    end
  end

```
